

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

D3.1

Protocol 2: Cultural Game

Jam Kit

EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam
Processes, Phases, Methods,
and Tools (Initial protocol)

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 10109505

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Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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1st Edition 2024

Grant Agreement ID: 101095058

Project DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3030/101095058>

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This publication can be viewed online and downloaded as pdf.

Please visit www.epic-we.eu

How to cite this report:

Nørgård, R. T. & Holflod, K. (2024). Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit. EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Initial protocol). EPIC-WE Horizon Europe Project. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14161689

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Technical References

Deliverable title	Protocol 2: Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Initial protocol)
Document type	Report
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Work package	WP3 – Ecosystems, Interventions and Methods
Task	T3.2
Lead beneficiary	AU – Aarhus University
Contributing beneficiaries	NISV; MEET; CBC
Authors	Rikke Toft Nørgård & Kim Holflod, Aarhus University, Danish School of Education, Denmark (AU)
Due date of deliverable	31.12.2023
Actual submission date	10.04.2024
Reviewed by	Andy Dockett (AUAS), Conceicao Costa (UL), Eva Erikson (AU), Carlos Coutinho (CMO), Bruno Silva (CMO), Aline Albertelli (KEA), Nélío Codices (BS)

PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document History

Version	Date	Status
V1	05.12.2023	First full draft
V2	15.12.2023	Second revised version following review by WP3; T3.1 Task Participants
V3	05.04.2024	Third revised version following review by Executive Board
V4	10.04.2024	Final revised version following review by Advisory Board and Coordinator
V5	10.04.2024	Submitted final version

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
EPIC-WE	Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments
TH	Triple Helix
QH	Quadruple Helix
DBR	Design-Based Research and Innovation
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
LL	Living Lab
CLL	Cultural Living Lab
HEI	Higher Education Institution
CI	Creative Industry
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institution
YC	Youth Citizens
CH	Cultural Hub
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam
CGJ Kit	Cultural Game Jam Kit
EPIC-WE CH	EPIC-WE Cultural Hub
EPIC-WE CGJ	EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam
EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem	EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem

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Introduction

01

1. Introduction

T3.2 Development of cultural game-making processes [Leading: AU; Participating: NISV, CBC, MEET; M8-12 & M20-24]. This task transforms 'existing/good practices' from design, game design and other relevant domains into the EPIC-WE Game Jam Kit that will be applied, iterated, and refined in all CGJs. The EPIC-WE Game Jam Kit draws on existing resources, toolkits, and repositories that are re-designed and transformed to target the aims and ambitions of the EPIC-WE CGJs and support CHI, CI, HEI, and youth in cooperating, collaborating and co-creating games through culture, and games for culture in local sites.

This deliverable and protocol from T3.2 draw from the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) performed in WP2. The SLR describes how operations manuals for existing and previous serious game jams are important to EPIC-WE regarding design, guides, and logistics, and it further provides inspiration for potentially valuable tools to the EPIC-WE game jams to facilitate ideation processes and values-conscious design. Moreover, a key lesson from the SLR is that the problem space of a game jam should be stated before defining the design and research protocol. While the SLR provide few tangible and applicable methods, templates, guides, or processes, it provides detailed descriptions and analyses on developing and executing game jam events in a collaborative and QH framework; this entails a reflective design process towards the design and remix of phases, transition tools, categories, and methods elaborated and extended in the present T3.2 deliverable. However, on a final note, the SLR accentuates that adapting its results into an EPIC-WE context is crucial for meaningful and relevant application.

WP4 will carry out local and glocal cultural game jams across three European sites in Denmark, The Netherlands, and Portugal to investigate the implementation, evaluation, and results of glocal-local cultural innovation ecosystems (T3 .1), glocal-

local cultural game jams (CGJs) for creating games through culture and games for culture (T3.2.), and glocal-local Design-Based Research on these interventions (T.3.3).

The T3.2. Protocol includes developing and delivering a Cultural Game Jam Kit, including a cultural game jam process model, cultural game jam phases, cultural game jam methods, cultural game jam dimensions, and cultural game jam transition tools, respectively. This task uses state-of-the-art and good practices from WP2 to deliver a thorough protocol for carrying out cultural game jams on local sites. The protocol will support the project in developing and delivering six local EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams (EPIC-WE CGJ) that invites youth into game-making as culture-making through the creation of games through and for culture as a format to empower young people as youth citizens and co-creators of European culture in quadruple helix systems (QH). Through this, the project will deliver a validated framework of cultural ecosystems for local CGJs between YCs, CHIs, CIs and HEIs.

The "Deliverable D3.1 – Protocols for carrying out cultural game jams in local sites" consists of 4 public reports:

- The T3.1 report "Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation: EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs (Initial protocol)."
- The T3.2 report "Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Initial protocol)."
- The T3.3 report "EPIC-WE Research Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites (Initial protocol)."

- The T3.3 report “EPIC-WE Practical Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites (Initial protocol)”.

The four reports included in the “Deliverable D3.1 – Protocols for carrying out cultural game jams in local sites” support the EPIC-WE project in carrying out its research and innovations.

1.1. The EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams

As its core activity, the EPIC-WE project develops, executes, and refines Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) for youth citizens (age 16-25) wherein they create games through and for culture with inspiration from cultural heritage. In CGJs, Youth Citizens (YCs) co-create games *through* and *for* culture with peers from diverse backgrounds and as partners in games and culture. Through this, YCs are positioned as game-makers and culture-makers in cultural heritage. The project's ambition is to develop and carry out CGJs so that YCs can experience and develop empowered participation and an enhanced sense of belonging in culture and cultural heritage. By inviting YC to become partners in culture-making and cultural heritage, EPIC-WE aims to equip them with cultural-creative imagination and competencies to engage in cultural and societal challenges with curiosity, creativity, agency, and imagination – what EPIC-WE frames as *Empowered Participation*.

The project explores the values and potentials of CGJs by pursuing the following goals:

- **Supporting** YCs in becoming co-creators of European culture by engaging in game-making as a form of culture-making and collaborating with Creative

Industries, Cultural Heritage Institutions, and Higher Education Institutions in Cultural Hubs (CHs).

- **Fostering** empowered participation by bridging the domains of games and culture in CGJs.
- **Positioning** CGJs as a cultural environment and model for youth to develop cultural empowerment, creativity, capabilities, and innovation.
- **Enriching** the domains of games and culture through the creation of games through and for culture by hosting CGJs.
- **Manifesting** the values of culture, cultural organisations, cultural heritage, and culture-making in fostering empowered cultural participation for YCs.
- **Delivering** models, processes, methods, and tools for executing CGJs that support and promote the above goals.

The design and execution of CGJs within the EPIC-WE project will be targeted towards the following value propositions:

- **Game-making as a form of culture-making** that develops cultural engagement, creativity, and empowered participation through CGJ processes, methods, and tools.
- **Games through and for culture** as a validated and equal form of cultural expression alongside other forms of cultural heritage.

- **Youth's belonging and empowered participation** in European culture and cultural heritage by way of cultural game-making and participation in CGJs and CHs.

In the EPIC-WE CHs (as elaborated in the T3.1 report “Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation: EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs (Initial protocol)”), Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), Creative Industries (CIs), Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), and Youth Citizens (YCs) work closely together in equal partnerships to envision and create new formats for cultural engagement, participation, and co-creation in the form of games through and for culture. EPIC-WE is carried out as a Design-Based Research and Innovation (DBR) project across three European CHs in Aarhus (Denmark), Hilversum (Netherlands) and Óbidos (Portugal), where the CH partners co-create new models and processes for cultural participation and innovation. Consequently, the format of CGJs is developed, tested, evaluated, and iterated as a promising and powerful approach to cultural partnerships, participation, and innovation for CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and YCs. Overall, the EPIC-WE project advocates for partners in research/HEIs, culture/CHIs, games/CIs, and the public/YCs to join forces, work together, and empower each other in Cultural Hubs and Quadruple Helix Ecosystems.

This involves:

1. The design of the EPIC-WE framework on the macro level, The EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem (EPIC-WE QH Cultural Innovation Ecosystem),
2. The design of the EPIC-WE framework on the meso level: The EPIC-WE CH Model (EPIC-WE CHs) and

3. The design of the EPIC-WE ecosystem on the micro level: The EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams (EPIC-WE CGJs).

While the protocol for 1) and 2) is described in the T3.1 protocol “Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation: EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs (Initial protocol)” (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024), the protocol for 3) will be described in this report. Taken together, the EPIC-WE framework on the macro, meso, and micro levels specifies how CHI, CI, HEI, and YC can work together as partners in cultural-creative innovation and transformation.

Accordingly, the T3.2 protocol will specify on the micro level how CHIs, CIs, HEIs and YCs will work together as partners in CGJs and how YCs, through engaging with the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit, will take on the role of cultural-creative participants and innovators by creating games through and for culture. The EPIC-WE CGJ Kit includes:

1. **The EPIC-WE CGJ Process Model** functions as a general model that visualises and connects the various phases, dimensions, categories, tools, and methods involved in organising a CGJ.
2. **The E-P-I-C Phases** guide YCs through the game design stages of Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create, which involve creating games through and for culture.
3. **The W-E Dimensions** accentuate and develop the dimensions of cultural Worlds and Empower participation in the YCs game-making process.

4. **The EPIC-WE Categories** focus on the YCs' empowered game-making and culture-making participation within the categories of Citizenship, Values, Culture, and Games.
5. **The EPIC-WE Transition Tools** that assists YCs in transitioning their work from one game jam phase to the next and towards their CGJ Expo as they are participating in the CGJ.
6. **The EPIC-WE CGJ Methods Collection** provides the YCs with the necessary methods for engaging in game-making as a form of culture-making, enabling them to create games through and for culture.

1.2. Structure of the report

The T3.2 protocol within the D3.1 report is structured around initially describing and visualising the developed EPIC-WE CGJ **model** that consists of four distinct **phases** that frame the cultural game-making process of CGJs. From here, the protocol frames the dual **dimensions** of creating new culture-game environments and worlds enabling youth empowerment. These dimensions permeate the four phases of the CGJ Process Model. Moreover, the protocol contains the novel concept of **transition tools**, which are tools designed to act as mediators between phases and enable YCs meaningful and reflective transitions from one phase to the next. The phases, dimensions, and tools thus constitute the core elements of the EPIC-WE CGJ Process Model. The protocol further describes and discusses multiple diverse methods that have been mapped, examined, redesigned, and iterated as tangible processes to navigate and guide each phase. The protocol's appendix lists numerous varied methods, along with their initial design and applications.

Finally, the report argues that the EPIC-WE CGJ Process Model is flexible and can be adapted and applied reflexively across different contexts, themes, and implementations.

EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit

02

2. EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit

2.1. Section Summary

In this section of the D3.1 T3.2 report, the CGJ Process Model is described, explained, and discussed. The model consists of four distinct phases: 1) Experience, 2) Play, 3) Imagine, and 4) Create – the EPIC phases. The progression through phases is taxonomical in nature by building upon existing and created knowledge, materials, and experiences from the phases before.

As an underlying and mediating element of the Process Model, the W-E Dimensions, 1) Empowerment and 2) Worlds – are established. They seep through all phases and are cultural dimensions that guide and permeate with a focus on enabling youths to participate in empowered participation and the creation and exploration of (new) worlds – in culture, games, between diverse people, and in CGJs.

The section further highlights the CGJ Categories and Transition Tools. The Categories emphasise the four focus areas of CGJs in 1) Culture, 2) Citizenship, 3) Games, and 4) Values, while the Transition Tools are materials and objects that mediate collaboration and game-making across and between phases. The transition tools are tangible materials and processes and are defined and developed as 1) Ideation Wheel, 2) Expert Council, 3) Playtest, and 4) Log & Pitch.

2.2. Introduction to EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit

Games exert a profound influence as cultural artefacts, shaping worldviews and values while impacting players' ethics, identity, and broader culture. On the one hand, they can bring about positive transformations, fostering empowerment, social inclusion, global citizenship, and promoting values. On the other hand, games

possess the potential for adverse effects, contributing to disempowerment, exclusion, intolerance, and even persuasive indoctrination. This duality is evident in concepts like toxic game cultures and #GamerGate, contributing to societal culture conflicts. Despite these challenges, the research underscores the promising potential of games to nurture cultural appreciation, drive positive societal change, and provide spaces of commonality and belonging.

EPIC-WE strategically builds upon this understanding, recognising games as dynamic value systems and cultural worlds that can positively shape culture and society. It adopts an innovative approach, viewing games as reflexive and dynamic objects within culture. It focuses on the dual role of games as cultural value systems and expressive enactments of culture. Through Cultural Game Jams (CGJ), cultural contexts, and value-sensitive methods, EPIC-WE positions games as integral components of culture, engaging YCs in game-making practices that connect with cultural heritage institutions and the creative industry. By fostering transformative partnerships and ‘meetings in the middle’ between CHIs, CIs, and HEIs (see the T3.1 protocol), the project explores the potential of games *through* culture and games *for* culture as pathways for empowered participation in cultural domains through CGJs.

A game jam is a co-creative event where game-makers come together to ideate and create (video) games within a set time frame (Kultima, 2015). The goal of a game jam is to encourage creativity, experimentation, and the rapid development of game concepts and prototypes (Merilainen et al., 2020). Participants may generally work individually or in teams and are usually given a specified theme or creative constraints that must be incorporated into their games. Game jams can vary in duration, with some lasting just a few hours while others span a weekend or even a week. The compressed time frame so central in game jams encourages participants to focus on essential aspects of game conceptualisation and development, such as the core

narrative, gameplay, or aesthetics, without getting bogged down by extensive planning, coding, or polishing. These events also often foster a sense of fellowship and community as they provide a platform for individuals to come together to develop and showcase their skills, learn from others, and receive feedback on their creations (Kultima, 2018, pp. 146-147; Merilainen et al., 2020).

Many game jams create innovative and unique game concepts and prototypes that may be further developed and matured after the event concludes. EPIC-WE aim to create, execute, deliver, and iterate CGJs that emphasise cultural concepts and prototypes wherein game-making is deeply connected to the domains of art, heritage, values, youth citizenship, and empowered cultural participation. This approach forms a multifaceted and novel approach to game-making and game jams, as concluded in the EPIC-WE Systematic Literature Review (presented in the project's D2.1 and D2.2 reports).

This calls for a sound but flexible protocol for *CGJs in and across local sites* and how a game jam process might be structured and analysed – as 1) problem space, 2) jam design (guiding criteria and logistics), 3) jam delivery and outcomes, and 4) follow-up opportunity (Reid et al., 2020). Here, the T3.2 protocol is focused on exploring, developing, and delivering a methodological framework – in the form of the EPIC-WE Game Jam Kit – that aims to emphasise and promote cultural heritage, values, and citizenship in game jams. As such, it extends the findings of the SLR into the practical domain through a game jam kit for executing CGJs. Through this, the protocol seeks to explore new innovative pathways for game jam facilitation within the cultural domain – and potentials for cultural participation, belonging, empowerment, and citizenship.

As stated in the EPIC-WE project description (Grant Agreement, 2023, p. 103), the Indicator Framework on Culture and Democracy (IFCD 2020) highlights the pivotal role of culture in championing European values and bolstering democratic societies through artistic expression and innovation. The Indicator Framework draws attention to the critical importance of encouraging the involvement of YCs in Europe's rich cultural heritage and shared cultural and societal values. Such involvement engages historical roots, actively shapes the present, and lays the foundation for collective Cultural futures. Through CGJs, EPIC-WE introduces approaches that are attuned to the value of culture and cultural heritage, creating new cultural environments where youth can develop capabilities essential for their future life and overall well-being. This, in turn, enables them to become active participants in European culture and society (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012; European Commission, 2019; Schutz et al., 2019).

Harnessing the power of games and their potential for shaping youth's cultures, values, and identities, EPIC-WE offers frameworks and methodologies for empowering young individuals to explore, create, and share games through and for a culture that celebrates cultural diversity and innovation while aligning with European values and lifestyles. Notably, the EPIC-WE project description highlights that even though game jams and game design are not necessarily novel in a QH setting, the integration of cultural value(s) and heritage is (Grant Agreement, 2023, p. 105). Here, cultivating productive connections and relations between game-making and culture-making through 'meetings in the middle' and co-creation between CIs, CHIs, HEIs, and YCs remains limited. Additionally, models, methods, and tools for how values can be woven into and expressed through game jams and games are underdeveloped (Lai et al., 2021). There is a striking absence of defined models and methods for game jams specifically geared towards culture, cultural

heritage, or cultural values, despite some existing examples from the literature (e.g., Kultima & Laiti, 2019).

As a response to these potentials and gaps, EPIC-WE develops, tests, and delivers protocols for Cultural Innovation Ecosystems, Cultural Hubs, and Cultural Game Jams, as well as how to research and refine these (the four D3.1 protocols). In the specific research and innovation context of EPIC-WE, and towards co-creating a novel and sustainable model for CGJs within a QH innovation ecosystem, a **Cultural Game Jam Kit for CGJs** has been developed. This kit includes a Cultural Game Jam model with **four distinct phases**: *Experience*, *Play*, *Imagine*, and *Create* (E-P-I-C) to support the creation of games through and for culture. The model's two **dimensions** of cultural *Worlds* and cultural *Empowerment* (W-E) work thematically across the four phases. The CGJ model, with its phases and dimensions, is thus a framework that invokes the EPIC-WE abbreviation. Four transition tools have been developed to help the participants navigate through the CGJ and transition from one phase to the next. The transition tools are integrated into the CGJ model for more scaffolded, meaningful, and productive transitions. Finally, each CGJ phase contains a selection of targeted CGJ **methods** which are developed to ensure that the game jam participants are creating games through and for culture (e.g., by focusing on the integration of cultural values, making games through the use of cultural heritage, or working to change current culture(s) through games).

In the following section, this protocol first describes and elaborates on the 1) development process of the EPIC-WE Gam Jam Kit; from there, the aim is to 2) define and describe its model, phases and dimensions – from the beginning of the CGJ towards the final exposition of games through and for culture; 3) hereafter, the transition tools are explained and elaborated; 4) the method collection is presented,

framed, and extended; 5) and finally, different approaches in applying the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit in flexible ways are presented and discussed.

2.3. Development of the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit

T3.2 focuses on the development of cultural game-making processes by transforming insights and results from existing practices, the EPIC-WE SLR and CGJ interventions into a protocol for CGJs in the form of a Cultural Game Jam Kit (CGJ Kit). To achieve this, T3.2 furthermore draws inspiration from an extensive collection and analysis of existing methods, tools, resources, and kits that target design, game-making, culture-making, values, citizenship, and cultural participation in different ways. This EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit thus aims to facilitate CGJs and support CGJ participants in the creation of games through and for culture through the integration of cultural values, heritage, and citizenship. In the CGJ, CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and YCs are positioned as co-operating and co-creating epistemic partners (Estalella & Criado, 2018), with the CGJ Kit acting as a driving and scaffolding framework.

Adhering to the EPIC-WE methodological framework of Design-Based Research (e.g., McKenney & Reeves, 2019) – the development of the CGJ Kit is iterative – continuously materialising, testing, evaluating, and revising it through insights from both CGJ research (WP2) and CGJ interventions (WP4).

The EPIC-WE Game Jam Kit has been developed through engaging the EPIC-WE project's described core ambition, objectives, and outcomes in relation to existing practices and methods regarding youth empowerment, creative and arts-based inquiry and design, processes and methods in design and making, cultural collaboration and innovation, game design and prototyping, along with several other domains, themes, foci, and challenges that EPIC-WE focus on and work with.

The EPIC-WE Game Jam Kit builds upon surveying and analysing existing design and development process models. Moreover, the model is heavily influenced by existing literature and practices within design processes, game-making, value-sensitive design, contemporary research and innovation projects addressing playful and creative learning and development environments, and experiential processes and methods in speculative design, play design, evocative design, educational design, arts-based design, game design and similar.

These existing models, templates, and guides have then been adapted and aligned to the cultural domain to position game-making as a specific form of culture-making. To develop the EPIC-WE model and Cultural Game Jam Kit, existing models, processes, phases, methods, and tools need to be adjusted, transformed, or innovated – including their language, descriptions, and goals – to express, target, and bring into being *cultural* game jams, game-making as *culture-making*, and games through and for *culture*.

The development of the T3.2 protocol began with a large-scale mapping of existing models, processes, methods, and toolkits from across the abovementioned domains. The large-scale collection of 64 different resource toolkits and repositories was then critically analysed and curated into a focused list of 26 highly relevant and promising toolkits and repositories (each one containing a substantial quantity and range of methods and approaches). From here, the collection was closely read, coded, and reviewed. Methods and approaches that showed great potential (if adjusted, transformed, or further innovated) in relation to the EPIC-WE target domain were highlighted. The highlighted methods and approaches were then coded based on their relevance and applicability in regard to the EPIC-WE phase of experience, play, imagine, create and the EPIC-WE core categories of culture, games, values, and citizenship. The analysed and coded methods were then compiled and organised into

a so-called ‘Toolkit Library’. This process yielded approximately 90 diverse methods and approaches detailed and documented in a spreadsheet.

	Title	Comment	Link
1	Methods and tools for co-producing knowledge	Relevant toolkit in inter-, multi- and transdisciplinary collaboration and co-creation	https://naturalsciences.dk/co-producing-knowledge-explained/
2	rustoolkit : Tools for better thinking	Collection of thinking tools and frameworks to help you solve problems, make decisions and understand systems.	http://rustoolkit.co/
3	design method toolkit	The Digital Society School Design Method Toolkit enables you to get started and enrich your design process. A collection of design and research methods: designmethod to help you select time-based to help you plan. Plan and execute your design research, ideation, experimentation, and creation within short iterations.	http://toolkits.ds.cloud/design/
4	designkit	Human-centered design is a practical, repeatable approach to arriving at innovative solutions. Think of these Methods as a step-by-step guide to unleashing your creativity, putting the people you serve at the center of your design process to develop new answers to difficult problems.	https://www.designkit.org/methods.html
5	CUTE toolkit	from site: Taking a strategic approach towards supporting the development of digital competencies of higher education teachers.	https://cutetoolkit.hu.dk/
6	Fuel4Design	Today's context, conditions and complexities need designers who can anticipate, enact and propose means and actions for shaping alternative futures by design. DESIGN FUTURES LITERACIES takes this up conceptually, pedagogically, pragmatically and critically. Relevant article: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0924646020300202	http://www.fuel4design.org/ http://www.fuel4design.org/index.php/futures-design-toolkit-access-toolkit/
7	innovation toolbox University of Copenhagen	The toolbox was developed as a part of the Next Generation project during the period Sept. 2012 – Sept. 2013 by Karsten and TEACH (former Katja), both based at the University of Copenhagen in collaboration with WorkZ (concept development), Stakeback (web development) and Marie Plomberg, UCPH HUM (graphics). In addition, the development happened in collaboration with teachers based at Copenhagen Business School (CBS), the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) and the University of Copenhagen (UCPH).	https://innovationep@uh.sites.hu.dk/method/
8	Innovator's Toolbox by Board of Innovation	An open-source innovation toolbox - some tools are AI-powered to generate novel insights and extend creativity between humans and machines.	https://www.boardofinnovation.com/tools/
9	Service Design Tools by Qolo	Diverse toolbox for design and innovation. Also has an enhanced toolbox.	https://servicedesigntools.org/tool/
10	Method Library by This is Service Design Doing	54 hands-on descriptions. Methods include instructions, guidelines, and tips and tricks for research, ideation, prototyping, and facilitation activities.	https://www.thisisservicedesign.com/methods
11	Hyper Island Toolbox	a toolbox to do things more creatively and collaboratively in their team or organization. It's a collection of methods and activities based on Hyper Island's methodology.	https://toolbox.hyperisland.com/
12	Design. Think. Make. Break. Repeat.	The methods included in the book and on this website are being contributed by leading experts in the field, boasting many years of experience in design research and practice. The exercises and templates are informed by the learnings from over fifteen years of teaching courses on design in the Design Lab at the University of Sydney.	http://designthinkmakebreakrepeat.com/methods
13	Mitre Innovation Toolkit	aims to cultivate and share proven mindsets, methods, and processes that help make innovation more approachable, effective, and fun for all.	https://itk.mitre.org/toolkit/

In conjunction with this process, several sectorial roundtables with partners and experts from Creative Industries, Cultural Heritage Institutions by partners and experts from Creative Industries, Cultural Heritage Institutions and Higher Education Institutions were conducted. The aim of the roundtables was to engage existing expertise within the Quadruple Helix sectors and document and capture existing and good practices in relation to the macro, meso, and micro levels of EPIC-WE (the D3.1 protocols). The sectorial roundtables yielded 38 additional resources and repositories, each containing a range of different methods and approaches.

██████████ a design kit - concrete tools - methods - playbooks - or other that ensures real afterlife and transfer/transformation ...much more than academic papers!!! ██████████

Definition

██████████ Continue to define concepts to build a common language within the project.

Mapping of complex relationships (stakeholders, goals, partnerships, concepts, ecosystems etc)

The legacy of the project - to keep the energy going after the project is formally finished. Local partnerships could be key in achieving this goal, since they are in close contact with young people on a on-going basis, even over several years.

Eva will return to the question of language - establish a shared language for ALL stakeholders. We are using concepts that mean different things for different stakeholders. We need to be aware of these differences. What works for the youth might be the language that works also as project language?

Remember that 4druple helix-partnerships are made from equal and different partners, so to become a living ecosystem takes trust which transpires from the recognition of having a similar goal but different stakes and expectations

██████████ - ANONYMOUS

Main key takeaway for me is to take this importance as impact as soon as possible in the current stage as youth inclusion and holistic change on cultural game-jams importance in participatory culture co-creation with youth. ██████████

OBJECTIVE 1: ASSESS

Explore & research the potential of games and game-making practices to empower youth and contribute to the strengthening of European values and cultural participation.

Your recommendations?

What would create / be of PARTICULAR value for HEIs?
What to focus on?

Recommendations for success?

Recommendations for value-creation for HEIs?
What would be recommendations for something to FOCUS on if we want to achieve the EPIC-WE objective?

Do you have existing recommendations, guidelines, policies, resources that EPIC-WE could draw on to achieve specific elements of its ambition - or achieve its objective in a specific way?

clarify what we mean by empowered youth - what criteria to value that - ANONYMOUS

change in level of agency in youth - ANONYMOUS

Allow the youth to bring their own themes - ANONYMOUS

These resources and repositories were also analysed and curated, to then be named and organised into the Toolkit Library.

Overall, the development of the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit involved multiple rounds of collecting, coding, curating, and compiling the Toolkit Library in conjunction with sector experts' and EPIC-WE partners' comments, reviews, and revisions of said Toolkit Library. The iterative process of materialising the initial protocol for the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit has been carried out through cross-sector collaboration, inter-disciplinary interrogation, and partnership co-creation. As part of this integrative review and revision process, the 12 partners of the EPIC-WE Consortium coming from CIs, CHIs and HEIs were asked to use their expertise and 1) perform a Dot voting of selected methods from the Toolkit Library and 2) comment on the relevance and importance of the dot voted methods. Dot voting is a way to easily

rank or deduce shared opinions within a range of options (such as potential game jam methods) in order to then choose the options with the most dot votes.

Stormdraining	Play	All	The inverse of brainstorming, reduce a large collection of ideas, activities, or components to a smaller collection of the most valuable or promising ideas.	Mitre Lab	https://itk.mitre.org/toolkit-tools/stormdraining/	X X X
Break up / Love letter	Experience	All	Instead of directly asking people what they like or don't like about a particular brand, product or service, this method gives insight into their perceptions by eliciting feelings based on real-life experiences and interactions through writing a love or breakup letter.	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/break-uplove-letter/	X X
Collage	Experience	All	A collage involves sticking images or words on to a large piece of paper, in order to group ideas, personal experiences, feelings and associations around a specific theme or topic.	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/collage-2/	X X
Storyboarding	Imagine	All	Stories add a human element to design and data analysis activities. They foster empathy and let designers walk in the users' shoes, increasing understanding of needs, activities, interests, and pain points.	Mitre Lab	https://itk.mitre.org/toolkit-tools/storyboarding/	X X
Moodboard / Moodspace	Play / Imagine	All	A Moodboard is a collage of images, words and/or even samples of materials. It helps you form an emotional image of the intended design. The overall 'feel'.	Design Method toolkit	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/moodboard-2/	X X X
Concept sketch	Play	Combining the 4	A concept sketch is a fast freehand drawing.	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/concept-sketch-2/	X
Dark side	Play	Culture / Values	The dark side turns your challenge into a negative one, forcing you to look at it from a refreshing angle.	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/dark-side/	X X
Mashup (another name: meshwork)	Play	All	The Mash-up brainstorm technique randomly combines different categories into one concept providing you with a range of unexpected ideas.	Design Method Toolkit	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/mash-up/	X X
Day in the life	Play	Citizenship	A study in which the designer observes the participant in the location and context of their usual activities, observing and recording events to understand the activities from the participant's point of view.	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/dav-in-the-life/	
Empathy map	Play	Citizenship	An empathy map is a tool to help a design team to empathize with the people they are designing for. You can make an empathy map for a group of people or for a persona.	Design method toolkit	https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/empathy-map-2/	X X

To ensure cross-sector, cross-hub, and inter-disciplinary convergence in the selection of potential Cultural Game Jam methods, all sectorial partners were asked to go through the proposed methods and "dot vote" the methods they judged to be particularly relevant, meaningful, or context-specific when it comes to Cultural Game Jams. The dot voting and commenting were carried out in a shared online and dynamic text document, the T3.2 Method Catalogue, acting as a common repository of potentially relevant methods, where partners had unlimited votes (however, only 1 per entry). In this way, it was possible for a partner to vote for all potential methods if they were all deemed of equal importance for EPIC-WE CGJs. Simultaneously, with the dot voting, partners were also asked to reflect and comment on the reasoning behind their votes in favour of specific methods. This was done to gain deeper and

more granular insight into why partners found specific methods particularly relevant for EPIC-WE CGJs.

Based on the EPIC-WE Consortium's dot voting and commenting, the Toolkit Library was iterated and further targeted towards the four E-P-I-C phases of the EPIC-WE Game Jam Model. Consequently, the results were analysed and synthesised, and based on this, between 10-20 methods for each of the four E-P-I-C phases were singled out and compiled into the initial EPIC-WE CGJ Methods. The methods collection is described and explained in detail later in this document, and in particular, in section 6, the methods and their connections to the CGJ Kits process model, phases, and categories are elaborated on and displayed in Appendix 10.1-10.4.

Each method included in the CGJ Kit will ultimately and after thorough research and development revisions, target and support CGJ participants in:

1. **Facilitating** cultural game-making within a specific CGJ phases: Experience, Play, Imagine, Create.
2. **Focusing** on cultural game-making within specific categories: Culture, Games, Values, and Citizenship.
3. **Scaffolding** participants' creation of games through and for culture along the CGJ dimensions: cultural worlds, cultural empowerment.
4. **Organising** their CGJ process through allocating specific time frames (e.g. 30-60 minutes), step-by-step descriptions (e.g. for brainstorming or prototyping), materials to use, etc.

5. **Reflecting** on game-making as culture-making through including critical-creative prompts and questions that widen and deepen participants' game-making process, thinking, and products.

2.4. Defining and Describing the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process

Model

Alongside the initial EPIC-WE CGJ Methods, the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model was developed. Similarly to the methods, the Game Jam Process Model underwent multiple iterations, leading to its maturation. During the development process, three different versions of the model were presented, reviewed, and revised. Version 1 contains the guiding principles supporting the development of the model. Version 2 showcases different visualisations of the model, and version 3 presents the revised and tested model included in the initial protocol.

Version 1 was developed through an ideation process and resulted in three initial principles to guide the following co-creation of the process model situated within the CGJ Kit:

1. The model will structure and divide CGJs into a 4-phase process similar to leading design process models.
2. Each phase in the CGJ will contain different objectives, methods, steps, and outcomes.
3. The model's different elements will be 'coded' in different ways (e.g., colour, icons, or naming) to highlight specific game jam stages, roles, dimensions, focus areas, or similar.

4. The CGJ process model should include all the elements of the CGJ Kit, assist in running CGJs, and centre CGJ participants game-making on the creation of games through and for culture.
5. The initial CGJ process model will be tested and evaluated with CGJ participants in local game jams, which should lead to further revisions.

Version 2 was a preliminary materialisation of the principles put forward in the first version. Here, the principles were further concretised, and the model was prototyped into some first visualisations. This iteration led to the following:

1. **E-P-I-C phases:** The four distinct phases – Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create – of the CGJ process were named and established.
2. **W-E dimensions:** The two distinct cultural dimensions – Worlds, Empowerment – of the CGJ process were named and established.
3. **CGJ categories:** The four focus areas – Culture, Citizenship, Games, and Values – of the CGJ process were named and established.
4. **CGJ transition tools:** The four transition tools – Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, Log & Pitch – were named and established.

The visualisation of 1-4 in a CGJ process model was prototyped, leading to multiple preliminary visualisations.

Figure 2: Version 1 of Process Model Draft

Figure 1: Version 2 of Process Model Draft

Figure 3: Version with contextualisation of the phases.

The conceptualisation, materialisation, and visualisation of the CGJ Kit and process model resulted in the below synthesised and approved EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model.

Figure 44: The EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model (Nørgård & Holflod, 2023)

The EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model is developed as a progression and taxonomical model that scaffolds the game jam process for CGJ facilitators and participants. It comprises four distinct cultural game jam phases, two foundational cultural dimensions, four focal point categories, four phase transition tools, and the concluding exposition, where the participating YCs will showcase their created concepts or prototypes for games *through* and *for* culture.

In the following sections, the different elements of the CGJ Kit and process model are described in greater detail.

EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Phases

03

3. EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Phases

3.1. Section Summary

This section delves into, extends, and elaborates on the four phases of the EPIC-WE CGJs: Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create. These phases follow a structured progression where each phase builds upon the previous, aimed at engaging participants in culture-making through tangible and collaborative game-making. The E-P-I-C phases combine divergent and convergent thinking to ideate and design games, game ideas, and game concepts. *Experience* initiates cultural exploration through divergent brainstorming, drawing on experiential ways of knowing and learning, while *Play* focuses on rapid exploration, iteration, and refining ideas into initial game concepts. The two initial phases are considered divergent ideation and design processes. *Imagine* focuses on game design through a more convergent approach to ideation and synthesises ideas into playable prototypes, whereas *Create* emphasises the final development, prototyping, coding, and creation of games for culture in CGJs, along with the last documentation of the process and outcomes. The final phase leads into the EXPO, where participants display and discuss their playable prototypes of cultural games.

The CGJ process model reflects established design processes like the Double Diamond and Design Thinking models, approaching divergent thinking for creativity and convergent thinking for decision-making. These processes are integral to game-making, supporting participants in materialising cultural game prototypes through tangible and concrete design elements, interactions, narratives, mechanics, and technologies.

3.2. Introduction to EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Phases

This section presents and discusses the four phases of the EPIC-WE CGJ: Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create. The phases have different objectives and outcomes and are connected in a taxonomical framing where each phase builds upon the previous, with an emphasis on engaging in culture-making through tangible game-making.

The E-P-I-C phases combine divergent and convergent thinking within an ideating and design domain. Here, Experience targets culture and cultural heritage exploration through participants' divergent ideation and brainstorming within the four EPIC-WE categories, while Play aims to focus this exploration into emerging cultural (heritage) concepts through participants' convergent ideation to integrate elements from the four categories into a game idea. Similarly, Imagine targets game worlds and game-making through participants' divergent design and game mock-ups towards games through and for culture, while Create transforms design ideas and game mock-ups through participants' convergence on a single game concept and playable prototype to be showcased at the concluding CGJ Expo.

Accordingly, the EPIC-WE CGJ process model mirrors dominant design process models such as the Double Diamond design process model from the Design Council (2007) or the Design Thinking process model from IDEO (2015). In general, divergent thinking involves creatively exploring and brainstorming numerous ideas without constraints, encouraging open-mindedness, inventiveness and the generation of a diverse range of possibilities. Divergent thinking values imagination, quantity and diversity over feasibility, comprehensibility and uniformity, allowing for wild and unconventional thinking. In contrast, convergent thinking is more analytical and decision-oriented, aiming to narrow down options systematically and logically to arrive at the best solution. Convergent thinking prioritises critical examination, evaluation, and decision-making, focusing on the creation of a valuable and viable

product. Divergent and convergent thinking are crucial in game-making, game design, problem-solving, and creative processes towards idea generation and decision-making. In EPIC-WE CGJs, such processes are integrated and executed through the four CGJ phases, supporting participants in the tangible materialisation of cultural game prototypes through imagining and creating concrete game ideas, aesthetics, designs, interactions, narratives, and mechanics.

3.3. Experience Phase

This phase engages experiential and imaginative ways of knowing, specifically through evoking youth participants' experiences with culture, art, heritage, games, citizenship, and values, which form the central foci of the CGJs. The exploration involves engaging and understanding cultural (heritage) experiences and actively enabling and creating new ones in situ with sector partners from creative industries, cultural heritage institutions, and higher education institutions. The experiential elements of the phase thus have a dual perspective on 1) the participant's own lived cultural experiences as vital in connecting and exploring games, culture, values, and citizenship, and 2) the articulation and mediation of potential new cultural (heritage) experiences during the early parts of the CGJ to lay out a foundation for empowered participation and innovation with games as, through, and for culture. Drawing on perspectives from dialogic design cultures (Manzini, 2016), the multiplicity of YCs voices and perspectives are actualised through lived experiences in the CGJ environment and positioned as essential in the creation of novel ideas, multivocal understandings, and inter-disciplinary cultural co-creation and collaboration.

The overarching aim of the Experience phase is to establish an understanding and positioning of culture and game-making within cultural worlds through cultural explorations. The Experience phase opens up to YCs' explorations of games as,

through, and for culture. This cultural foundation will then guide later CGJ phases and participatory processes, directing them toward creating cultural games within context-specific heritage sites that differ in culture, heritage, values, thematic specificity, and expected processes and outcomes.

3.4. Play Phase

Following the Experience Phase and the participants' exploration of its possibility space with the Ideation Wheel transition tool comes the Play Phase. Play is an ambiguous concept that signifies and evokes different things in different contexts. In this phase, play is approached as an inherently collaborative and communal phenomenon that is decidedly experimental – thus connecting to the previous phase. Through its playful characteristics, the Play Phase invites allow for diverse modes of exploration, experimentation, creativity, collaboration, and relationality. Research shows that interdisciplinary and interprofessional teams working through playful methodologies inspired by the characteristics of play can connect across differences and boundaries more easily (Holflod, 2022), which is of central importance to EPIC-WE as it aims to invite youth from diverse backgrounds, interests, situations, and life-worlds to connect and co-create novel games that explores, innovates, and transforms culture, art, and heritage.

In this phase, harnessing the power and attitude of play (James & Nerantzi, 2019; Sicart, 2014; Nørgård, 2021) means creating a processual, open-ended, explorative, and experimenting cultural environment for participants to 1) play around with games and game-making as culture-making, 2) play with diverse and particular cultural/societal values, and 3) embody cultural citizenship as empowered participation. Here, 'playing around' might take the form of brainstorming, collage-making, sketching, tinkering, mashups, or storyboarding games and culture with

European values and citizenship, and wondering what might be otherwise, transformed, or enacted differently in mediating culture, games, values, and citizenship.

From an etymological point of view, the activity of *play* also resonates with gameplay and cultural playworlds, which conceptualise play as a community of playfellows who explore and experiment together to try things out and toy with culture through the act of game-making.

The overarching goal and intended outcome of the Play Phase is the materialisation of a tentative idea for game, culture, and values intertwined concept and the formulation of a concept pitch for said idea. This convergence on specific games through and for culture concepts is highly important as the transition tool of the Play Phase is the Expert Council, where CGJ groups have an audience with experts within the CGJ domain. Here, the CGJ groups pitch their concept for a value-sensitive game through and for culture that experts from CIs, CHIs, and HEIs then give critical and inspirational feedback on to substantiate and strengthen the group's iterative game development during the CGJ.

3.5. Imagine Phase

The third phase of the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model accentuates *imagination*. However, it is not the immaterial imagination of thought and wonder, but the materialisation of participants' experience and play through the creative imagination of a game through and for culture that transforms, re-works, and enacts values, citizenship, and culture. Through this phase, participants are supported by CGJ methods to engage in empowered cultural participation and embodied cultural citizenship through game-making. Here, participants work towards creating a mock-

up that can be evaluated through playtesting. In the Imagine Phase, they are supported by methods for experience mapping, prototyping, and mock-ups to arrive at a game concept that can playtest the gameplay experience, cultural world, and empowerment dimension that participants seek to bring to life in their game through and for culture. The game concept to be playtested targets the four categories of game-making: art/cultural heritage, aesthetics, mechanics/system, and story.

While the previous two phases of Experience and Play evoke divergent exploration and convergent experimentation within the domain of culture, the Imagine phase is applied to enable divergent exploration within the domain of game-making, moving from multiple game ideas and mock-ups to a single game through and for culture in the form of a game concept or playable prototype. Here, the playtest acts as the transition tool between the Imagine and Create phases of the game-making process. Thus, this phase aims to transform their divergent and convergent exploration within the cultural (heritage) domain into divergent and convergent experimentation within the game (design) domain through emphasising playtesting the elements of culture, values, and citizenship through interacting with and experiencing diverse cultural worlds and environments.

3.6. Create Phase

In the final phase, Create, the participants integrate results from their playtesting into their game concept and work towards creating and showcasing an experiential or playable prototype for a game through and for culture. Towards this goal, they are supported by different methods such as paper prototyping, video pitching, interactive prototypes, concept art, and game showcase exposition. This is then materialised through presenting and exhibiting their game through and for culture at the concluding Expo, supported by the transition tool of Log & Pitch. The Create phase

highlights the convergence on a single (playable) prototype that audiences can experience and play with at the Expo. Therefore, this phase should predominantly focus on deepening, elaborating, enriching, and reinforcing the core game idea – its core interactions, aesthetics, technology, and story – to formulate and create a coherent and innovative game through and for culture.

A vital part of this phase and its processes is the documentation of the development process in a Game Log to capture how the created games materialise and connect to cultural values, heritage, and citizenship, with preparing and staging a Game Pitch of the created game through and for culture at the Expo.

EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Dimensions

04

4. EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Dimensions

4.1. Section Summary

This section of the protocol presents the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit Dimensions and Core categories, highlighting its objectives and elements. The CGJ Dimensions are designed to provide a unique and enriching experience for young people to engage with cultural heritage and create culturally significant games and gaming experiences. The W-E Dimensions, which stand for World and Empowerment, serve as focal points, guiding participants through the game jam process. The World dimension frames the development and materialisation of cultural-creative worlds, which are expected to carry values, meaning, and relevance, contributing to a vibrant cultural heritage while addressing European values. Games and game worlds possess a distinct ability to transcend boundaries and shape youth citizens' cultural and societal perspectives. The Empowerment dimension promotes a sense of cultural 'becoming' — experienced as empowered participation with cultural heritage during the CGJ. It aims to evoke a sense of cultural 'belonging' in young people, encouraging them to generate propositions and products for cultural-creative worlds and citizenship. This dimension aims to foster cultural value, meaning, relevance, and affinity, contributing to young people's engagement with the appropriation of European values, cultural heritage, and citizenship.

The EPIC-WE CGJ Dimensions and Categories sustains an underlying cultural awareness in the CGJs, highlighting the cultural world-making, world-building, and worlding that permeates and influences the participants' game-making during the CGJs. Here, the EPIC-WE CGJ Categories serve as practical orientation devices for participants in the game jam, guiding them in aligning their creative endeavours with the overarching goals of empowered participation in culture and the generation of culturally significant games and gaming experiences.

4.2. Introduction to EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Dimensions

The **W-E Dimensions** play a crucial role in shaping the game jam into a Cultural Game Jam (CGJ), functioning as distinctive cultural lenses that infuse the E-P-I-C Phases with a particular atmosphere and direction. The cultural World dimension and the cultural Empowerment dimension serve as focal points in the game jam process, guiding participants through the process of ideating, conceptualising, materialising and consolidating game-making as culture-making as they navigate the E-P-I-C Phases during the EPIC-WE CGJ.

The W-E Dimensions serve a dual purpose. Firstly, they act as the overarching 'aims and ambitions' for YCs participating in the EPIC-WE CGJ. This involves promoting a sense of cultural 'becoming' — experienced as empowered participation with cultural heritage during the game jam (games through culture). From this, the W-E Dimensions aim to evoke a sense of cultural 'belonging' in YC, encouraging the generation of propositions and products for cultural-creative worlds and citizenship (games for culture). Combined, the CGJ dimensions are intended to foster cultural value, meaning, relevance, and affinity, contributing to YCs engagement with appropriation of European values, cultural heritage and citizenship.

Secondly, the W-E Dimensions function as practical 'orientation devices' for participants within the CGJ. The dimensions work together with the CGJ phases to generate a structured approach to reflective decision-making throughout the creation of cultural game ideas, concepts, prototypes, and final products. By serving as a cultural navigation tool, the W-E Dimensions guide the CGJ teams in aligning their creative endeavours with the overarching goals of empowered participation in culture and the generation of culturally significant games and gaming experiences.

4.3. World Dimension

The World dimension frames the development and materialisation of cultural-creative worlds (games for culture) that are expected to carry value(s), meaning, and relevance, contributing to a broader and vibrant cultural heritage while addressing European values.

Games and game worlds possess a distinct ability to transcend boundaries and shape youth citizens' cultural and societal perspectives. Operating as particular cultural realms, game worlds (games as culture) – and their inherent culture and values – influence our sense of belonging, ethics, values, and identities, both within and beyond the confines of the game world. The games we engage with convey messages and foster communities that, in turn, shape our experiences. As cultural worlds, games are central and important cultural products that impact players' ethics, identities, and worldviews.

Games and gameplay can bring about real cultural and societal change by fostering empowerment and social inclusion towards global citizenship and belonging, providing a reflection on values and diversity. However, games also hold the potential for darker elements of disempowerment, exclusion, intolerance, and sexism. In this way, games serve as potent vehicles of culture and values that impact our society's cohesion, values, and culture, both inside and outside their game worlds. Nevertheless, these darker aspects of gaming stand in contrast to the favourable facets and advantages that games offer. They can act as instruments of cultural socialisation, promoting cultural appreciation, serving as catalysts for real-world change, advocating for diversity, and creating environments for communal interaction, empathy, and a sense of belonging. Concepts such as games for good,

game-based learning, games for change, and woke gaming highlight the potential of such more positive impact of games.

In creating cultural environments for young people to conceptualise cultural worlds and become culture-making game-makers, CGJs offer valuable processes and approaches. Within the CGJs, players actively enact and game worlds interactively encapsulate cultural heritage by engaging with both tangible and intangible heritage. This approach necessitates Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs) to open up their spaces to game-makers 'jamming' with cultural heritage and exhibiting their games through and for culture.

As such, the 'World' dimension of the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model sustains an underlying cultural awareness in the CGJs – and thus helps materialise (inter)personal worlds for cultural socialisation, historical and current worlds of culture and heritage, cross-sector and inter-disciplinary worlds for 'meeting in the middle' at the CGJs. In other words, the World dimension highlights the world-making, world-building, and *worlding* that permeates and influences the participants game-making during the CGJs. Moreover, the different cultural heritage sites in the EPIC-WE project (such as the ARoS Art Museum in Aarhus, Denmark or Óbidos, UNESCO City of Literature in Portugal) contribute with unique cultural environments, themes, and heritage. In the Aarhus Cultural Hub, a core aim of the CGJs is 'Games for European values, game worlds as identity-shapers, and cultural game environments as spaces of being and belonging', while Hilversum targets 'Games for democratic participation, game worlds as society-shapers, and cultural game environments as spaces of community and inclusion', and Obidos highlights 'Games for cultural participation, game worlds as culture-shapers, and cultural game environments as spaces for cultural appreciation and creation'.

4.4. Empowerment Dimension

The second dimension of the model is 'Empowerment'. EPIC-WE aims to empower youth citizens (YC) by engaging them in cultural game-making activities to inspire and invite their cultural, creative, and civic participation. The ambition is to empower YCs to participate in cultural and societal challenges with curiosity, creativity, agency, and imagination, or what is framed as "Empowered Participation" within EPIC-WE. In the EPIC-WE project description, the concept of empowerment – and empowered participation – is described accordingly:

EPIC-WE introduces cultural game jams, culture- and value-sensitive game-making and games through and for culture as a novel approach to empower young people as co-creators of European culture and shapers of their own futures in society, cultural institutions (CHIs) and creative industries (CIs) [...] Together EPIC-WE engage in cultural games jams to create games through and for culture inspired by cultural heritage. The framework explores the potential of this approach as a method for strengthening European values, belonging and cultural participation. Through game-making activities, EPIC-WE will equip youth with cultural-creative imagination and competencies to face societal challenges with curiosity, creativity, agency and imagination – what we call Empowered Participation.

EPIC-WE utilises games and game-making to encourage empowered participation in culture, cultural heritage, and cultural institutions among YCs who may initially feel disempowered or disengaged from these areas. As such, EPIC-WE aims to improve youth involvement in culture and gaming by inviting them to become "cultural game jammers," through the creation of games through and for culture. Consequently,

EPIC-WE takes a distinctly cultural approach to empowered participation, aligning with the concept framed within cultural participation, citizen participation, and audience engagement domains. Positioned within the realms of culture and cultural heritage, the project explores game-making as a form of culture-making and examines the potential of game jams to facilitate engaged and empowered participation in culture.

The concepts of empowerment and participation are interwoven, and complementary processes and outcomes (Pettit, 2012) and connect to, e.g., elements of personal and collective growth, relationality, transformation, and emancipation (Martínez et al., 2017). Here, EPIC-WE is particularly targeting a democratisation of research and innovation through empowered and equal transformational partnerships across sectors, disciplines, and domains to imagine alternative cultural environments and worlds: critically, reflexively, and with care for the collective future (DiSalvo, 2022).

As the Grant Agreement outlines, EPIC-WE seeks to foster cultural participation and empowerment for youth citizens (YC) and those who may not initially identify with culture, cultural heritage, or cultural institutions. The project aims to enable YCs to participate actively in cultural processes, contribute to shaping European culture, and co-create their futures through game-making and culture-making.

This dimension of the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model thus highlights the critical elements of approaching, scaffolding, and experiencing cultural empowerment during game jams – and, importantly, how YCs can become increasingly more culturally empowered participants during such processes and through engaging, creating, and shaping European values, cultural heritage, and games for culture. Like the dimension of 'Worlds', this dimension acts as an underlying part and principle of

the CGJs that affect, influence, and seep into the methods, approaches, and activities – specifically and generally.

4.5. CGJ Core Categories

EPIC-WE approaches culture, citizenship, games, and values as four focus areas and core categories that focus on the participants game-making and culture-making in the Cultural Game Jam (CGJ). Furthermore, the four sectorial partners (YCs, CIs, CHIs, HEIs) constituting the Quadruple Helix (QH) partnership, enacted within the Cultural Hubs and through the Cultural Game Jams, are each positioned as experts in one of the four core categories. An expertise they bring with them into the CGJ:

- Creative Industries bring into the CGJs their expertise in games, game design and games as culture;
- Cultural Heritage Institutions bring into the CGJs their expertise in culture, cultural heritage and games through culture;
- Higher Education Institutions bring into the CGJs their expertise in value(s), value-sensitive and games for culture;
- Youth citizens bring their expertise in citizenship, cultural belonging, and empowered participation into the CGJs.

Combined, the four core categories represented by the QH partners in the EPIC-WE project become materialised as *orientations* in the CGJ Kit and contextualise its featured methods when it comes to focus areas, thematic directions, and concrete application. The four categories thus have a dual aim and function in the model.

Firstly, they represent and actualise the QH partnership and innovation ecosystem as a cultural living lab or Cultural Hub that enacts specific roles before, during, and after the CGJs with CHIs as *culture*, YCs as *citizenship*, CIs as *games*, and HEIs as *values*. *Secondly*, they are also the four focus areas of the game-making processes and, as such, the four *lenses of orientation* that the games through and for culture – the products of the game jams – must explore, transform, integrate, and express. In this way, the core categories resonate with the macro level of the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and the meso level of the EPIC-WE Cultural Hubs as described in the T3.1 protocol “Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs (Initial protocol)” and manifest themselves on the micro level in the cultural game-making practices within the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams.

However, participants in the CGJs must be supported and guided in transitioning from one phase to the next in a cumulative way. Here, the EPIC-WE CGJ Transition Tools serve as tools for participants to catch, condense, and carry with them their game-making and culture-making thinking and practice from one phase into the next. The next section will introduce and describe the EPIC-WE CGJ Transition Tools.

EPIC-WE Transition Tools

05

5. EPIC-WE Transition Tools

5.1. Section Summary

The EPIC-WE Transition Tools are objects and processes that provide *transitions* between phases and strengthen the overall game development in the Cultural Game Jams (CGJ). Each E-P-I-C Phase ends with a transition tool that captures, focuses, and extends the participants and their cultural game jam processes into the next phase.

EPIC-WE CGJs employ four transition tools to help participants navigate between the different phases of the game design process. These four tools include the Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, and Log & Pitch. Each tool serves a unique purpose in facilitating the transition from one phase to another and contributes to the overall success of participants' game design process towards showcasing their created games through and for culture. Each tool provides concrete, actionable outcomes and valuable insights that enhance the game concepts as games through and for culture.

5.2. Introduction EPIC-WE Transition Tools

Transition tools are objects and processes that serve as a bridge between phases and functions to strengthen and focus participants' processual development of games through and for culture. They are tangible, functional, and actionable tools that the Cultural Game Jam (CGJ) participants use to move forward into the next phase of the CGJ. Transition tools play a critical role in supporting the development of games through and for culture by creating a bridge between the different phases and functions of the Cultural Game Jam (CGJ). These tools are tangible, functional, and actionable, allowing participants to move forward into the next phase of the CGJ with greater focus and clarity.

The EPIC-WE Ideation Wheel is a computational, hands-on, and explorative tool that bridges the first and second phases of the CGJ. Drawing on similar design tools from play research and educational research and development, the Ideation Wheel is designed to examine multiple potential ideas in between games, culture, values, and citizenship. It builds on material tools for idea generation and their early history, scientific groundings, and practical verifications. The Ideation Wheel is a material visualisation of ideas and concepts of playful approaches to learning and how it was explicitly ideated and conceptualised during the early parts of the R&D project.

The EPIC-WE Expert Council is designed to support the transition from the second to the third phase of the CGJs. It builds on concepts and approaches from 'Design Crits', 'design studio crits,' 'design arguments,' and 'design demonstrations.' The EPIC-WE Expert Council transitions CGJ participants from the third to the last phase of CGJs and enables feedback for improvement, enhances team culture, and fosters a positive and productive atmosphere, ultimately contributing to the refinement of design ideas. The feedback received during critiques encourages designers to think creatively and may lead to more innovative choices in the design process.

The EPIC-WE Playtest transition tool supports the transition from the third to the last phase in the CGJs and is crucial for achieving a balanced and enjoyable gaming experience, as it facilitates the collection of valuable information through feedback forms, enabling designers to refine and enhance the gaming experience. Playtest supports the overall game design process by testing game prototype elements and ensuring that the intended gaming experience is being achieved.

The EPIC-WE Log & Pitch tool is the final transitional tool in the game jam process model. It moves CGJ participants from the game design process into the final CGJ

Exposition. This involves creating a comprehensive Game Log (see appendix 10.9) in the form of a design document to ensure effective communication and pitching of the overall games through and for culture vision among team members.

Overall, these transition tools are critical to the success of the EPIC-WE project, allowing participants to move forward through the different phases of the CGJ with greater focus, clarity, and purpose. In the following sections, we will take a closer look at each of these transition tools and explore their specific features and benefits in more detail.

5.3. Ideation Wheel: Transitioning from the Experience Phase to the Play Phase

The EPIC-WE Ideation Wheel is the first transition tool, which connects and mediates the first and second phases of the CGJ. Drawing on similar design tools from play research and educational research and development, the ideation wheel is a computational, hands-on, and explorative tool for examining multiple potential ideas in between games, culture, values, and citizenship. It draws scientific, practical, and designerly inspiration from concepts/materials such as playwheels, ideation tools, and algorithmic tools for problem-solving – originating from the "Ars Magna" (Lull, 1232-1316) - that act as computational tools to compute ideas and concepts (Christensen, 2023) with aims of extending imagination and possibilities within the CGJs and across its phases. It thus builds on material tools for idea generation and their early history, scientific groundings, and practical verifications (Benet, 2011; Uckelman, 2010; Sales, 1997) and the 'Playwheel' (Playful Learning Project).

In the sector-wide Danish research and development program Playful Learning, the PlayWheel has become an iconic tool for the exploration of play and playfulness in

experimenting and creative learning design with each circle/wheel representing a theme, e.g., playful learning context, methods, approaches, and expected outcomes. The PlayWheel is a material visualisation of ideas and concepts of playful approaches to learning and how it was explicitly ideated and conceptualised during the early parts of the R&D project at one of the six university colleges (Ørsted & Laybourn, 2021). Consisting of four rings, each with six different categories and an empty field, the wheel potentialises almost 2500 different combinations.

In a recent PhD dissertation, this algorithmic ideation tool was also explored and iteratively designed for higher education teachers and students in the humanities (Christensen, 2023). Here, Christensen argues that providing tangible computational tools to humanities students enhances their ability to generate ideas and fosters divergent thinking. This approach, identified as a crucial "idea creation technique" for 21st-century students, supports skill development in effective communication and collaboration. Additionally, the computational thinking method challenges students to embrace diverse perspectives and integrate peer input into their work, promoting an ethos of openness and responsiveness.

In EPIC-WE, the aim of the ideation wheel is similar, emphasising the development of a simple, tangible material design to support vast numbers of ideas and configurations of games, values, culture, and citizenship. One ring in the ideation wheel will display the eight European values; thus, eight options will be in the values category. The other three rings and categories regarding games, culture and citizenship will contain between 4-8 possibilities, thus allowing for what might almost appear as infinite ideation outcomes - and therefore, multiple ways of imagining games as/for culture - in the CGJs.

5.4. Expert Council: Transitioning from the Play Phase to the Imagine Phase

The EPIC-WE Expert Council builds on concepts and approaches from 'design crits', 'design studios,' 'design arguments,' and 'design demonstrations' (see, e.g., Cennamo & Brandt, 2020; Healy, 2016). A design critique (abbreviated as 'crits') generally evaluates a design's alignment with contextual or experiential objectives and user needs, offering feedback for improvement. This collaborative process can enhance a design team's reflection and design judgment, ultimately contributing to the refinement of design ideas. The feedback received during critiques encourages designers to think critically and creatively and may lead to more substantiated or innovative choices in the design process. However, conducting an effective design critique session can be challenging, as designers – here, young game-makers – may assume that not everyone shares their understanding of design processes, the language of criticism, and the protocols involved in a critique. This entails a need for clarity, division of roles and responsibilities, and careful balancing between fostering empowered participation through evaluative approaches while still guiding the game design ideas and conceptualisations towards the project's emphasis on games, culture, values, and citizenship.

Design studios—sometimes likened to design critiques—emphasise peer evaluation, reflection, constructive criticism, and iteration. In this context, students or participants present a product or a proposed solution and receive immediate feedback from both experts and fellow students (McLain, 2022). This process is often structured as peer feedback and formative evaluation, aiming to 1) explore different possibilities under the assumption that the initial solution may not be optimal and 2) enhance solutions through repeated formative feedback. The Expert Council in the CGJs draws on the design studio and designcrit as a method for sharing, evaluating, and strengthening

ideas and possible solutions, with experts coming from each of the quadruple helices represented in EPIC-WE.

5.5. Playtest: Transitioning from the Imagine Phase to the Create Phase

Designers conduct different evaluations throughout the entire game design process to determine if the intended gaming experience is being achieved. Here, playtesting offers valuable insights that enhance the gameplay, gameworld and gaming experience. For instance, playtests help answer questions about whether the gameplay works as intended, whether the intended gaming experience is achieved and whether the gameworld is engaging, balanced, and cohesive (Grogorick et al., 2018).

Playtesting generally involves different groups of individuals who can positively contribute to the playtesting of a game's core concept, overall gameplay or developed playable prototype, depending on the game design phase and the game's maturity. Initially, developers playtest the game amongst themselves, offering insightful feedback on the core game concept. At later stages, game jam teams might ask each other to playtest mock-ups or prototypes of the game, exploring undiscovered aspects. The ultimate playtesters are the target audience, capable of offering detailed insights into player experience and preferences. Various playtesting methods exist, such as one-on-one and group testing, each with distinct advantages. Whether quantitative or qualitative, feedback forms facilitate the collection of valuable information, enabling designers to refine and enhance the gaming experience (Eckardt et al., 2018).

In an educational game-making setting, Eckardt and Robra-Bissantz (2018) argue that the iterative design process of incorporating playtests is crucial for achieving the strived for gaming experience with educational elements. Here, emphasis should be placed on testing and iteratively designing with the target audience to proximate the intended interaction and experience, even though it is also characterised by extended development times and significant use of resources.

Though EPIC-WE is not an *educational* design and research project, it may be relevant to draw upon created knowledge adjacent to it by integrating perspectives on the importance of playtests for understanding, iterating, and substantiating games – for culture.

In the EPIC-WE CGJs, playtests act as the third transitional tool to transition game-makers from the third to the fourth phase of the CGJ. The EPIC-WE Playtest Transition Tool draws primarily on the foundational game design handbooks 'Game Design Workshop' (Fullerton, 2018) and 'The Art of Game Design' (Schell, 2008) in combination with the above perspectives and research. Throughout the third phase, Imagine, the participants collaborate towards creating a game concept, mock-up, or prototype that can be playtested. The playtest supports the overall game design process by testing the core game elements of interaction, technology, story, and aesthetics, along with the thematic foci of the game through and for culture and its intended interplay between citizenship, values, culture, and games.

5.6. Log & Pitch: Transitioning from the Create Phase to the Expo

The CGJs' end results are the created *games through and for culture* and an accompanying game *pitch and plaque*. The fourth phase concludes the cultural-creative process of making games through the use of culture and cultural heritage to

present a game for culture, cultural participation, and cultural empowerment. The final EPIC-WE Transition Tool is Log & Pitch and leads the CGJ participants from the game design process into the concluding CGJ Exposition where they will showcase and pitch their games to each other and/or visitors. The Log & Pitch transition tool is inspired by game design documentation, design logs, and elevator pitches of design and game concepts for an audience.

Fullerton (2018) states that effectively managing the game development process requires the ability to clearly communicate the overall vision, concept, and gameplay to team members, necessitating a written document (in the form of a game log) to ensure effective communication and coherent execution of vision and concept. The game designers iteratively create logs and update the design document throughout the game design process. The design team might make use of collaborative tools such as wikis, shared documents, or blogs to co-create and collectively manage design documents, track changes, and allow for the inclusion of text, images, and other media. Whether using a wiki, blog, or standard word processing software, the design document aims to detail the gradual conception and maturation of the game's innovative concept, core gameplay, intended player experience, target audience, story and gameworld.

Overall, Fullerton (2018) argues that a well-crafted design document serves as the solid blueprint for a game, providing a shared reference point for the entire team. It facilitates collaboration and meaningful discussions among team members, ensuring everyone understands how their individual tasks work towards the overall game. Team members may interpret the game differently without clear design documentation, leading to incoherent efforts. Such a lack of coordination can result in a game that does not meet the intended vision and specifications. To create an effective design document, the game designer collaborates with every team member

to ensure cohesion and achievability in their respective areas. This collaborative process generates communication, requiring team members to consider how their work fits into the overall game concept, from high-level vision to low-level specifications. Since game developers are typically visually oriented, supplementing the document with sketches, visualisations, storyboards, concept art, or gameplay flowcharts enhances understanding and communication.

During the final phase of the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model, the participants will prepare an *exhibition plaque* for their game through and for culture. Museum exhibits often feature plaques, which feature alongside the displayed artwork or artefact. These informative plaques typically provide contextualisation and descriptions alongside details such as the object's name, characteristics, date of creation, and creator. In this context, the plaque acts as a condensed version of the overall game log and pitch that aligns with museums' and cultural heritage sites' cultural contexts and atmospheres. The games through and for culture plaque, identify, describe, and elaborate upon the CGJ team's prototypes, concept art, gameplay interaction and experience connected to the EPIC-WE Dimensions and Categories, and thus present the CGJ team's overall vision, argument, and intended experience. This act of creating a plaque echoes the content of the Log & Pitch transition tool while also functioning as an object for communication and dissemination at the CGJ Expo, aiding the CGJ teams in the pitches of their games through and for culture to visitors and audiences.

Combined, the EPIC-WE Transition Tools that provide *transitions* between phases and strengthen the overall game development in the Cultural Game Jams. Each E-P-I-C Phase ends with a transition tool that captures, focuses, and extends the participants and their cultural game jam processes into the next phase.

From here, we now turn to how the participants might be supported in creating games through and for culture and how this might be operationalised within each phase of the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model. Hence, the next section introduces and discusses the EPIC-WE Game Jam Methods & Categories, which are the concrete, tangible, and context-sensitive methods that guide CGJ participants in their game-making and culture-making towards creating *games through and for culture*.

EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Methods

06

6. EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Methods

6.1. Section Summary

This section focuses on the development of the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam (CGJ) Methods and presents the development of the initial EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit consisting of the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model, the EPIC-WE Methods Guide, the EPIC-WE Role Cards, the EPIC-WE Transition Tools & Transition Capture Cards, and the EPIC-WE Group Game Logs. The EPIC-WE CGJ Methods Collection is a comprehensive guide that includes and describes relevant methods within the four E-P-I-C phases and core categories (values, games, culture, and citizenship) of the CGJ. The collection draws inspiration from existing methods repositories and toolkits from game design, educational design, values-sensitive design, co-design, etc., to inform its development and integrate existing practices and insights from prior research projects.

The EPIC-WE CGJ Kit comprises numerous methods and approaches that are transformed and adjusted to specifically target the cultural domain and the CGJ objectives and outcomes. The EPIC-WE Methods Collection targeting the E-P-I-C phases ensures a nuanced and tailored approach towards the designerly and practical aspects of ensuring the CGJs' relevance and sensitivity towards the EPIC-WE project aims and themes.

The project's compiled method collection serves as a comprehensive resource in the design and development process of the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit. The resulting EPIC-WE Methods Collection is designed to be a flexible resource to be applied across different contextual and thematic sites to support CGJs, participants' game-making as culture-making, and the creation of games through and for culture.

6.2. Introduction to EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Methods

The development process of the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Methods Collection is driven by an iterative approach, aiming to encapsulate the core ambitions of the project and its methodological foundations in Design-Based Research. The thematic focus of this collection is broad, covering the EPIC-WE Categories of values, games, culture, and citizenship. As previously described, the CGJ Methods Collection draws inspiration from existing methods repositories and toolkits from game design, educational design, values-sensitive design, co-design, etc., to inform its development and integrate existing practices and insights from prior research projects. All methods will be adjusted and transformed to align with the specific ambition and objectives of the EPIC-WE project, along with its diverse geographical, thematic, and conceptual CGJ interventions. Moreover, each Cultural Hub within EPIC-WE further redesigns, adapts, applies, and iterates the CGJ methods to fit the context-specific requirements and constraints of each hub, site, and CGJ, along with considerations of the participants, thematic foci, practical needs, and design considerations regarding space and place of the individual CGJ events.

During the EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Partner Roundtables, valuable feedback on existing best practices was gathered from all EPIC-WE partners, inspiring multiple co-design sessions with feedback cycles towards materialising the initial method collection. The refinement process involved dot voting and commenting along with several rounds of feedback, revisions, and comments from EPIC-WE partners and the Executive Board (EB). Finalising the EPIC-WE Game Jam Methods Collection involves testing and evaluating it through CGJs to further transform the CGJ Methods Collection for suitability towards the project's core aims and objectives, terminology, and conceptual positions. This entails:

- Evaluating and targeting all methods for further sensitivity and relevance towards the interplaying cultural dimensions and core categories of EPIC-WE.
- Extending and adjusting all methods regarding their foci, aims, expected outcomes, expectations and suggestions regarding time, materials, and spaces, as well as facilitation notes and guides to fit the CGJ process.
- Developing and delivering a flexible CGJ Methods Collection to be applied across different contextual and thematic sites to support CGJs, participants' game-making as culture-making, and the creation of games through and for culture.

The project's compiled toolkit repository, comprising documents such as the Toolkit and Resource Library, the Process of T3.2 EPIC-WE Game Jam Methods presentations, documentations of numerous expert panels, and Method Collection Appendices, served as comprehensive resources in the design and development process (see above section 2). The result is the initial EPIC-WE Game Jam Methods Collection, a comprehensive guide that includes and describes methods within the distinct phases and categories of the CGJ. These categories include EPIC-WE Method Categories (Values, Games, Culture, Citizenship), establishing a clear connection to cultural Dimensions and Transition Tools. Furthermore, the EPIC-WE Methods Collection targeting the E-P-I-C phases ensures a nuanced and tailored approach towards the designerly and practical aspects of ensuring the CGJs' relevance and sensitivity towards the EPIC-WE project aims and themes.

Crucially, the EPIC-WE Methods Collection is not merely a theoretical framework or off-the-shelf collection but is developed from research and existing practices and is designed to be iteratively tested, evaluated and refined through Design-Based

Research (DBR) on the CGJs. This DBR development process will ensure that the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit, including its Methods Collection, will align with the objective and intended outcomes of both the EPIC-We project and CGJs, providing a valuable resource for future projects and initiatives that share similar ambitions or objectives.

In the table below, the top-voted favourably commented and chosen methods are listed. As described in section 2 of this report, the methods in the list were selected through a meticulous process of collecting, analysing, categorising, and curating an extensive repository of methods from similar fields and practices. Following this, the curated collection underwent rounds of voting, reviews, and revisions, resulting in the table below of selected methods for the initial CGJ Kit. In the table, duplicates appear across phases, which signifies that specific methods are relevant for two or more phases. In the next step the selected methods will be transformed and adjusted to specifically target the cultural domain and the CGJ objectives and outcomes. Here, methods are renamed and rewritten to align with the specific game-making and culture-making practices within a specific E-P-I-C phase (see Appendices)

Experience (10)	Play (19)	Imagine (13)	Create (10)
Brainstorming	Brainstorming		
Break Up/Love Letter	Brainwriting		
	Cardboard Prototyping	Cardboard Prototyping	Cardboard Prototyping
Collage			
			Create a Pitch
	Dark Side		
		Design Principles	
	Dot Voting	Dot Voting	
	Empathy Map	Empathy Map	
	Idea Selection		
Make A World			

	Manifestos on values and ethics		
	Mashup / Meshwork		
	Moodboard / Moodspace	Moodboard / Moodspace	
			MoSCoW
	Paper Prototyping	Paper Prototyping	Paper Prototyping
Photo Safari	Photo Safari		
	Provotyping	Provotyping	Project Pinocchio
	Rapid Prototyping	Rapid Prototyping	
Rich Picture			
Roles & Responsibilities	Roles & Responsibilities	Roles & Responsibilities	Roles & Responsibilities
	Rough Prototyping	Rough Prototyping	
		Six Thinking Hats	
	Stormdraining		
	Storyboard	Storyboard	Storyboard
			Storywall
Visualising values in design with mood boards			
Walkabout			
			Poster Session
Lotus Blossom			

6.3. (Re-)Designing a Methods Collection for EPIC-WE

The EPIC-WE Methods Collection comprises numerous methods and approaches that are adapted, rewritten, and embedded in a particular CGJ phase: Experience, Play, Imagine, or Create. Some methods are ‘fluid’ or flexible as they span multiple

phases. For example, ‘brainstorming’ might be readily utilised in both the Experience and Play phase, functioning either as initial idea generation that combines elements of games, values, culture, and citizenship, but it might also be used later in the Play phase to generate novel ideas for new cultural game experiences, game mechanics, game aesthetics, or game narratives. Another example is methods like ‘Roles and Responsibilities’ which is a relevant and applicable method to implement during all E-P-I-C phases to support the group's different roles and responsibilities in the development of games through and for culture.

In the practical application of the Methods Collection during a CGJ, the collection of methods for each of the E-P-I-C supports the participants in bringing together culture, games, values, and citizenship to explore cultural worlds and environments and create games through and for culture. During the different E-P-I-C phases of the CGJ, the cultural game jam team should choose methods that correspond with the vision, intentionality, goals, and needs of the CGJ team. Each CGJ Method Card contains a general description, a brief how-to guide, guiding reflection questions, needed materials, potential outcomes, and when to use the method. Finally, a QR code can be found on each of the CGJ Method Cards in the collection, linking the CGJ method to academic references or designerly resources along with more details and further help. The complete initial EPIC-WE Method Collection with developed Method Cards for each CGJ phase can be located in the appendices of this report.

6.2.1. Experience

For the Experience Phase of the CGJ, 12 methods were singled out to be adapted and rewritten for their culture-sensitive application in the CGJ, addressing the interplaying categories of culture, citizenship, values, and games. The appendices display numerous visualisations of the methods, their EPIC-WE framing, context-

specific descriptions, and references. The 12 original methods are (see references and descriptions in Appendix 10.1):

1. Brainstorming
2. Break Up / Love Letter
3. Collage
4. Make A World
5. Lotus Blossom
6. Photo Safari
7. Rich Picture
8. Roles & Responsibilities
9. Visualising values in design with mood boards
10. Walkabout
11. Value Vocabulary
12. How might we...?

The overarching aims and goals of these methods are to generate novel game ideas that integrate perspectives on culture, collaboratively and rapidly, and in ways that connect the CGJ core categories of values, citizenship, culture, and games. Moreover, the methods are chosen as they, in different ways, might enable rich and reflexive considerations of cultural heritage, values, and worlds (if redesigned) and how this might influence a game and its design, narrative, aesthetics, and mechanics.

6.2.2. Play

For the Play Phase of the CGJ, 20 methods were voted and selected to be adapted and rewritten for application by participants in the CGJ, addressing the creative experimentation with themes of culture, citizenship, values, and games. In the appendices, the redesigned and rewritten methods for the Play Phase are listed

along with their EPIC-WE framing, context-specific descriptions, and references. The 20 original methods are (see references and descriptions in Appendix 10.2):

1. 6-8-5 Sketching
2. The Sketch Game
3. Cardboard Prototyping
4. Dark Side
5. Dot Voting
6. Empathy Map
7. Manifestos on Values and Ethics
8. Mashup
9. Moodboard
10. Paper Prototyping
11. Photo Safari
12. Provotyping
13. Rapid Prototyping
14. Roles & Responsibilities
15. Rough Prototyping
16. Stormdraining
17. Storyboard
18. Visualising values in design with moodboards

Combined, the methods in the Play Phase focus on the converging experimentation with ideas generated in the Experience Phase, which are developed further through collaborative processes. In this way, the CGJ methods in the Play Phase build upon the methods – and their results - from the Experience Phase to extend the CGJ Kit with methods specifically targeting sketching, moodboards and mock-ups for merging the domain of culture and gamed along with developing initial concepts for

narrative, aesthetic, interactive, and technical considerations. The overarching goal during this phase and thus the selected methods is to enable the co-creation of a cultural game idea that can be presented and critiqued at the Expert Council, functioning as a transition tool between the Play Phase and the Imagine Phase. As such, the methods and processes during this phase must lead to tangible ideas, concepts, and early prototypes in the form of mock-ups.

6.2.3. Imagine

For the Imagine Phase of the CGJ, 13 methods were chosen to be adapted and rewritten for application by participants in the CGJ, addressing the creative prototyping using the themes of culture, citizenship, values, and games. In the appendices, the redesigned and rewritten methods for the Imagine Phase are listed along with their EPIC-WE framing, context-specific descriptions, and references. The 13 original methods are (see references and descriptions in Appendix 10.3):

1. Cardboard Prototyping
2. Design Principles
3. Dot Voting
4. Empathy Map
5. Moodboard
6. Paper Prototyping
7. Provotyping
8. Rapid Prototyping
9. Roles & Responsibilities
10. Rough Prototyping
11. Six Thinking Hats
12. Storyboard
13. Visualising values in design with moodboards

During this phase, the goal of the methods and their applications are to use the work from the previous phases along with the feedback from the Expert Council to iteratively prototype games through and for culture while further integrating and refining innovative thinking within the domains of culture and games. This, in turn, leads to Playtesting of the prototype, marking the transition into the Create Phase. As such, the methods during this phase are applied with a divergent game-making approach, testing and adjusting the game concept and prototype to approximate the intended empowering gameplay experience, cultural world, and games for culture.

6.2.4. Create

Finally, the Create Phase of the CGJ contains 10 selected methods to be adapted and rewritten for application by participants in the CGJ, addressing the construction of the final game prototype, the production of a promo video, and the creation of a design argument for how the game uses culture as material and how it functions as a game for culture. In the appendices the redesigned and rewritten methods for the Create Phase are listed along with their EPIC-WE framing, context-specific descriptions, and references. The 10 original methods are (see references and descriptions in Appendix 10.4):

1. Cardboard Prototyping
2. Create a Pitch
3. MoSCoW
4. Paper Prototyping
5. Project Pinocchio
6. Roles & Responsibilities
7. Storyboard
8. Storywall

9. Visualising values in design with moodboards

10. Poster Session

The final Create Phase and its methods are chosen considering the YCs' completion of their game prototype, the creation of their game log and pitch using the transition tool, and their concluding presentation of their games at the CGJ Expo. Hence, the selected and redesigned methods target the finalisation of game concepts and prototypes and the group's publication, dissemination, and showcasing of them.

6.4. Visualising the Initial EPIC-WE Design Kit for the First Round of Interventions

The above Methods Collection is a collaborative, synthesised, and refined collection of gathered methods and approaches from research and existing practices to be adopted and adapted within the Cultural Hubs (CH) and their CGJs. While the overarching aims and goals of all EPIC-WE CHs are shared, a CGJ Kit to organise and run CGJs as an innovative format for culturally empowered game-making must be flexible, reflexive, and context-sensitive. Moreover, each CH has its own thematic foci, e.g., diversity and equality or intergenerational exploration, which the CGJ Kit needs to accommodate to engage and integrate the specific culture, context, situational constraints, and overall facilitation potentials of each CH and their CGJs. The following illustrates and discusses how the initial CGJ Kit was developed, iterated, and constructed within one of the CHs before it was tested and evaluated in the EPIC-WE project's first CGJ at the ARoS Art Museum in Aarhus, Denmark. As explained in earlier sections of the report, the CGJ Kit and its different elements, methods and materials draw from an extensive repository of existing methods and

approaches such as e.g., the “Design Method Toolkit”¹, “Service Design Tools” by Oblo² and the “Hyper Island Toolbox”³, with content and structural inspiration from e.g., “Fuel4Design”⁴, the “Design Kit” by IDEO⁵, “Untools”⁶ and the “Methods and tools for co-producing knowledge”⁷ toolkit.

The initial CGJ Kit developed for the first EPIC-WE CGJ in Aarhus included the following elements and produced materials:

1. The EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model (presented above)
2. The EPIC-WE Methods Guide
3. The EPIC-WE Role Cards
4. The EPIC-WE Transition Tools & Transition Capture Cards
5. The EPIC-WE Group Game Logs
6. The European Value Cards

The EPIC-WE Methods Guide is the initial ‘handbook’ of the CGJ process and methods, which introduces and explains the four E-P-I-C phases and presents possible methods to apply during each phase (see Appendices 5 and 6). In essence, the developed EPIC-WE methods for the initial CGJ are targeted refinements of the existing methods collection presented above. For the first CGJ, the existing methods presented above were used as inspiration for generating thematic and context-specific methods relevant to the creation of games through and for culture.

¹ Design Method Toolkit: <https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/>

² Service Design Tools: <https://servicedesigntools.org/>

³ Hyper Island Toolbox: <https://toolbox.hyperisland.com/>

⁴ Fuel4Design – Futures Design Toolkit: <http://www.fuel4design.org/index.php/futures-design-toolkit-access-toolkit/>

⁵ Design Kit – IDEO: <https://www.designkit.org/methods.html>

⁶ untools: <https://untools.co/>

⁷ scnat knowledge – Methods and tools for co-producing knowledge: <https://naturalsciences.ch/co-producing-knowledge-explained>

The EPIC-WE Role Cards (as seen below) introduce and specify the different roles that CGJ participants distribute amongst them in the CGJ team. Combined, the roles support the individual team members in focusing their work during the CGJ and promote practices of game-making as culture-making. The EPIC-WE Role Cards comprise five different roles, each with their own responsibilities and focal points in the CGJ: ‘Gamemaster’, ‘Storyteller’, ‘Artist’, ‘Designer’, and ‘Crafter’ (see Appendix 10.5). The aim of this division of roles and their accompanying responsibilities is to help participants focus on and emphasise the four core EPIC-WE Categories of *games*, *culture*, *values*, and *citizenship* while engaging in practical game design during the CGJ.

The EPIC-WE Transition Tools include the concrete manifestation of the tools along with a description of their application, whereas the EPIC-WE Transition Capture Cards function as aids for capturing and reflecting on the outcomes of utilising the transition tools. The Ideation Wheel is (for now) the most materially tangible of the transition tools, created to scaffold tangible exploration of game ideas that select and reflect on values, culture, and citizenship, while the three other transition tools are collaborative, interpersonal processes documented through the capture cards and in the final game design logs.

The EPIC-WE Group Game Logs are documents that describe how to document the game design and development process reflexively and collaboratively, as well as the

delivery of a reflexive and intentional concept and prototype for a game through and for culture.

Finally, the European Value Cards are a collection of cards, each presenting and describing one of the six European values⁸, along with reflexive questions to inspire robust, creative, and imaginative considerations of the values and their role in the CGJ team's cultural game design process. The picture below displays three of the European Value Cards and their structure, style, and content. The full collection is found in the appendices (Appendix 10.8).

Democracy

Democracy is a cornerstone of European values, embodying the principle that political power should ultimately reside in the hands of the people. This involves the right to vote in free and fair elections and the broader concept of civic engagement, encouraging citizens to participate actively in decision-making processes and ensuring a diverse political landscape.

Reflections:

- What role do art, heritage, and games play in nurturing a culture that values and enables democratic processes?
- How can art, culture, heritage, and games ensure inclusivity and representation, democracy and civic engagement?
- In what ways can citizens actively contribute to the improvement and sustainability of democratic governance?

Freedom

Within the European framework, freedom means more than the absence of oppression; it captures the protection and promotion of individual liberties. This entails the right to express opinions, make choices, and actively participate in societal affairs without unwarranted constraints, fostering an environment where personal autonomy is valued and preserved.

Reflections:

- How can a balance between individual freedom and the need for societal order and security be struck - and how might art, culture, and games address it?
- In what areas of life, culture, and games is freedom most crucial, and are there situations where restrictions may be justifiable?
- How can advancements in society and technology be managed to safeguard personal freedom and privacy in the digital age?

Equality

The European value of equality underscores the commitment to a society where all individuals enjoy equal treatment and opportunities regardless of their differences. It rejects discrimination and strives for fairness, fostering an inclusive environment that enables everyone to contribute and thrive on an equal footing.

Reflections:

- How might art, games, and cultural heritage help bridge existing inequalities within diverse communities?
- How can culture and games address systemic discrimination and promote a more inclusive and equal environment?
- How can games and culture aid in fostering fair, equal, and thriving communities and societies?

⁸ https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/principles-and-values/aims-and-values_en, visited April 9, 2024.

Combined, the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model, the EPIC-WE Methods Guide, the EPIC-WE Role Cards, the EPIC-WE Transition Tools & Transition Capture Cards, and the EPIC-WE Group Game Logs constitute the initial EPIC-WE CGJ Kit. The initial EPIC-WE CGJ Kit will be iteratively tested, evaluated, and refined through its application in several CGJs across multiple Cultural Hubs.

EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit in Action

07

7. EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit in Action

7.1. Section Summary

The EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit (CGJ Kit) is a versatile toolbox developed to foster youth empowerment and cultural participation through game creation. Implemented across three EPIC-WE Cultural Hubs, the CGJ Kit undergoes rigorous testing and evaluation via Design-Based Research interventions. These interventions, outlined in protocols, aim to synthesise knowledge on supporting youth in crafting games that reflect and enrich culture.

Three different approaches to operationalising the CGJ Kit is introduced and described: the open kit, targeted kit, and fixed kit. The open kit allows maximum freedom for participants to select methods, promoting autonomy but risking overwhelm. The targeted kit offers a curated selection, balancing open and closed processes. The fixed kit provides a structured pathway, ensuring cohesion but potentially limiting agency.

A pilot CGJ hosted by the Aarhus Cultural Hub demonstrated the CGJ Kit's application. Forty young participants engaged in a six-hour game jam focused on cultural heritage and the value of equality. Despite challenges such as information overload and pacing issues, all groups successfully developed concepts for cultural game, showcasing the potential for meaningful cultural exploration through game-making.

The EPIC-WE CGJ Kit, conceived as a flexible resource for organising and running CGJs, is intended for adoption, use, and evaluation with collaborative reflexivity and context sensitivity in each local Cultural Hub.

7.2. Introduction to EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit in Action

The next step in the development of the CGJ Kit is to implement, test, and evaluate it through CGJs across the three EPIC-WE Cultural Hubs. Here, the three Cultural Hubs will research and innovate the format of CGJs and the CGJ Kit through Design-Based Research interventions (McKenney & Reeves, 2019). Here, each hub focuses on different themes and has site-specific aims (presented and described in the D3.1 Protocol 1 (T3.1)). Through 12 CGJs functioning as Design-Based Research interventions in the EPIC-WE project, the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit will be developed, implemented, tested, evaluated, iterated, and refined. This entails that the interventions are accompanied by a sound research protocol (presented and described in the D3.1 Protocol 3 (T3.3)), as well as an assisting practical protocol (presented and described in the D3.1 Protocol 4 (T3.3.)) to identify and synthesise new knowledge on CGJs and how to support YCs in their creation of games through and for culture by way of the CGJ Kit.

The EPIC-WE CGJ Kit is developed and conceptualised as a flexible toolbox that can be adjusted, modified, and utilised to serve different approaches, themes, and contexts in each of the local Cultural Hubs. As such, there are multiple ways of preparing, incorporating, and performing the CGJ Kit in CGJs.

7.3. Ways of operating the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit

What does a CGJ look and feel like? What processes and practical considerations might create relevant foundations for youth-empowered cultural participation, collaboration, and innovation? And how do the Cultural Hubs and cross-sectorial partners (CI, CHI, HEI, YC) operationalise the CGJ Kit under consideration of the diverse expertise, thematic foci, and different temporal, spatial, and logistical

constraints? To approach the operationalisation of the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit – with the mentioned considerations in mind as highly influential and impactful regarding research, innovation, participation, and project aims – a reflective, flexible, and context-sensitive approach is needed. Hence, the CGJ Kit is designed to enable at least three distinct ways of adopting and utilising it: 1) the open kit, 2) the targeted kit, and 3) the fixed kit.

7.3.1. The Open Kit

This adaptation of the CGJ Kit seeks to facilitate a maximum of free choice and YC agency within the scaffolded CGJ process, emphasising both their individual and collective decision-making. This entails providing them with the entire repository of CGJ methods to choose from within each CGJ phase.

The advantages of this ‘open’ operationalisation of the CGJ Kit lies in its emphasis on YCs’ unrestricted, autonomous, agentic, and explorative processes in relation to picking and choosing CGJ methods as they see fit in relation to the specificities of the cultural theme, context, and environment, the group or individual preferences, and the reality of how their game-making and culture-making processes evolve over time. The intention of the Open CGJ Kit is ideally to facilitate YC experiences of empowered participation, self-ownership, and democratic co-ownership of the CGJ process emanating from the freedom to choose one's own path.

Some disadvantages of this approach might be that YCs become overwhelmed by the number of choices, complexity and lack of structure, given the pressure of the limited timeframe of game jams, the newness of the CGJ format and the lack of guidance. As a consequence, a too open CGJ Kit might work opposite of what is intended, leading to YCs experiencing loss of perspective, being encumbered and, in turn, becoming disempowered.

Accordingly, when applying this open setup, it is paramount to remain sensitive to the CGJ participants' experiences and processes, be flexible in changing the configuration to provide more scaffolding, as well as consistently provide mentoring and facilitation when needed.

7.3.2. The Targeted Kit

The second option is more 'targeted'. This adaptation of the CGJ Kit provides the CGJ participants with a curated selection of the CGJ methods where CGJ facilitators carefully choose a subset of methods for each of the E-P-I-C phases within the full collection of methods. This process requires thoughtful consideration from facilitators when it comes to 'targeting' specific cultural themes, game-making or culture-making processes, or specific YC needs, interests, and expertise. Here, facilitators need to work to ensure that the selected CGJ methods align with the target and goals of the CGJ when it comes to engaging and empowering youth in the context of CGJs in ways that contribute to the CGJs overarching goals of cultural innovation, values development, and cultivating a sense of citizenship within the context of the EPIC-WE CGJs. The Targeted Kit aims to provide YC with a more limited and curated selection of CGJ methods which they can choose from. The Targeted Kit allows for CGJ facilitators to ensure greater cohesion and more targeted processes in the CGJ while still leaving the choice between available methods up to the CGJ groups and participants.

The primary advantage of this 'targeted' approach is the open-ended but semi-controllable equilibrium of structure and anti-structure. Balancing the structured and an unstructured process in the CGJ setup may lead to a more supportive, creative, and collaborative space, providing YCs with more direction in their processes.

However, this structured-unstructured middle ground might also be Targeted Kits' main disadvantage. It has the potential for YCs to simultaneously experience a lack of structure and a lack of self-guided agency, leading to processes where YCs feel less empowered, given their more limited freedom, while also being unsure of what directions to take, given their open-endedness.

Accordingly, to apply the targeted CGJ approach, facilitators should put a lot of thought and work into curating methods and preparing the process to ensure that the right balance between the structured and unstructured is struck. Furthermore, facilitators should also work to ensure that the selected methods work towards the intended targets of the specific CGJ, that the methods support YCs in creating a cohesive game-making process within the E-P-I-C phases, and that the curated Targeted Kit scaffold the CGJ participants and facilitate their processes while still aiming for open-endedness, agency, and freedom to explore and decide.

7.3.3. The Fixed Kit

The third option is for CGJ facilitators to choose in advance the specific CGJ methods that all CGJ participants will use during the CGJ. This 'fixed' approach creates a maximum structured process that eliminates the need for YCs to spend the time on getting acquainted with, discussing, and deciding between a collection of methods. This frees up time for the CGJ group, which can be an advantage in a time-pressured process such as a game jam. Though the participants have no freedom when it comes to choosing between methods and creating their own pathways, the Fixed Kit is still tailored to scaffold and promote cultural empowered participation. Facilitators' creation of a carefully planned single pathway through the CGJ might provide YCs with the needed support in the unfamiliar process of game-making as culture-making and the creation of games through and for culture.

This might, in turn, actually foster more cultural empowerment, creativity, collaboration, and imaginative thinking compared to processes where all the work is put on the YCs. Adopting this approach allows the organisers to structure a cohesive and well-organized sequence of activities that emphasise EPIC-WE's core elements and ambitions and clearly address and equally focus on the interplays between culture, citizenship, games, and values. Clear and transparent CGJ planning furthermore eases and strengthens the practical and research processes and participants' experiences. As such, the Fixed Kit serves as a comprehensive roadmap, streamlining the CGJ experience and maximising engagement for a meaningful cultural and gameful exploration and creation.

However, the fixed structure and constraining elements might easily lead to experiences of disempowerment due to its lack of freedom, ownership, and agency. When using this approach, it is, therefore, vital to consider the sequencing and scaffolding of the methods and activities in ways that foster processes of maximum creativity, agency, diversity, and ownership of the final outcomes without diminishing the young people's voices and empowered participation.

7.4. Cultural Game Jam Kit in action: EPIC-WE Pilot & Playbook

The EPIC-WE Pilot Game Jam in Aarhus is a concrete example of (a mock-up of) the fixed kit in action. In December 2023, the Aarhus Cultural Hub hosted an EPIC-WE Pilot Game Jam, inviting 40 young people between the ages of 17-19 to a mini 6-hour game jam in Filmby Aarhus. The pilot was held to try out and do a 'proof of concept' of the very first mock-up of the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit. This setup is a concrete example of the enactment of the Fixed Kit and controlled process, the Quadruple Helix system, and the Living Lab model in action. The pilot was scaffolded by a

developed EPIC-WE PlayBook, which had a thematic focus on specifically selected cultural heritage artworks from ARoS Art Museum, the EU value of "Equality," along with YCs own 'cultural citizen artefacts' brought into the game jam by the YCs. The Godot Engine served as the chosen game engine within the pilot, and the YCs were here supported by game designers from Filmby Aarhus. The game jam process in the pilot was characterised by a focus on the integration of cultural heritage and the value equality in culture-making games. During the day, multiple representants from CHI (i.e., ARoS), CI (i.e., Funday Games, Filmby Århus, Ideas Lab, and Creative Business Network), and HEI (i.e., Aarhus University) participated and had different roles as e.g. facilitators, experts, speakers, judges, researchers, developers.

The EPIC-WE pilot showcased notable strengths. All seven groups succeeded in creating and presenting tangible game concepts or mock-ups focusing by way of creating games through culture (i.e. using the cultural heritage artworks as material) to present game for culture (i.e. games with cultural value(s) or aiming to create cultural change or innovation). Consequently, all groups were supported in the unfamiliar process of game-making as culture-making and succeeded in incorporating interactive game element showcasing their game ideas, visual style, narrative, and intended interactions. At the concluding showcase, the groups pitched their game vision, concept, gameplay and gameplayer experience to experts and each other, sharing and discussing the outcomes of the EPIC-WE pilot along with its challenges and potentials. The allocation of specific CGJ roles to each of the group members proved effective. The mock-up of the experience and play phases demonstrated a structured and focused process characterised by divergent thinking, exploration, and game conceptualisation. In contrast, the later phases moved the process and the participants towards convergent thinking and the materialisation of game concepts.

Despite its strengths, the EPIC-WE game jam pilot encountered specific challenges. Information overload and tight processes were notable, especially during later phases. Participants faced high and low energy stages, lacked breaks, and had an overall too stressful pacing through the different EPIC-WE phases. The game-making processes were highly intensive, with bursts of energy during experience and play but lower energy during imagine and create. Additionally, the CGJ mock-up in the form of the EPIC-WE Playbook needed revision and redesign to be more nuanced, particularly in storytelling. However, authenticity in youth voices was apparent and valued.

Several vital takeaways were identified from the EPIC-WE game jam pilot. It highlighted the importance of carefully designing and planning participants' interaction with culture/heritage and values. It pointed towards more in-depth cultural processes with specific cultural heritage pieces to ease the ideation of creating games through culture. The mock-up of the CGJ process was deemed meaningful, but there was room for substantiating and developing cultural, heritage, art, games, and values dimensions. In other words, though all groups and all game ideas and concepts were reflexive, agentic, and attractive to the Quadruple Helix partners and the game jam participants, they slightly lacked thematic and conceptual richness and substance. However, this was to be expected from the very compressed and limited timeframe of the pilot jam (5-6 hours) when compared to the time frame of a traditional game jam (24-48 hours). The participants' novel and experimental game concepts reflected the themes of EPIC-WE, emphasising the potential for future meaningful cultural and societal game development and exploration.

The next iteration of developing the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit involves practical implementation and evaluation across the three Cultural Hubs to thoroughly test, evaluate, iterate, and refine the initial CGJ Kit into a validated and matured version.

Concluding Summary

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8. Concluding Summary

This protocol, “Cultural Game Jam Kit: EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Processes, Phases, Methods, and Tools (Protocol 2 – Initial protocol)”, created within Task T3.2 in the EPIC-WE project, involves describing, explaining, and delivering the design of the micro-level EPIC-WE Ecosystem, explicitly focusing on the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit. This task outlines how Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI), Creative Industries (CI), Higher Education Institutions (HEI), and Youth Citizens (YC) collaborate at this level. YC, involved with the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit, plays a role as cultural-creative innovators and change-makers by creating games through and for culture. The components of this task include defining the EPIC-WE CGJ Process, Transition Tools, Categories, W-E Dimensions, and the CGJ Methods Collection. The goal is to transform existing practices into a coherent kit that aligns with EPIC-WE's objectives, utilising resources and repositories tailored to CGJs and youth participation.

Through "cultural game jams" and methods attuned to culture, context, and values, EPIC-WE positions games as integral to culture, involving young people in game-making practices that resonate with cultural heritage institutions and the creative industry. By fostering collaborations among cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, and higher education, the project seeks to uncover the potential of games within culture as avenues for empowered participation in cultural domains, mainly through CGJs.

Within the EPIC-WE Design-Based Research and Innovation framework, the initial protocol and model for Cultural Game Jams has been developed and described. The CGJ Kit includes the four E-P-I-C phases: Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create along with the W-E Dimensions of cultural worlds and empowerment and four core categories: Culture, Citizenship, Games, and Values, reflecting partner roles and lenses within the Quadruple Helix and Cultural Hub. The EPIC-WE CGJ Kit aspires

to be a sustainable model for running CGJs in accordance with the EPIC-WE ambitions and objectives. The CGJ Kit follows an iterative Design-Based Research approach, where it is continuously tested, evaluated, and refined through research into and practice of CGJs.

The first section is an introduction that provides an overview of the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jams and the report's structure. The second section introduces the development of the EPIC-WE CGJ Kit and presents the EPIC-WE Game Jam Process Model. The EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Phases section outlines the different E-P-I-C phases of a cultural game jam, including the Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create phases. Each phase is described in detail, with specific tools and methods outlined for each one. The EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Dimensions section focuses on the W-E Dimensions (cultural Worlds and Empowerment) of cultural game jams. The World Dimension is concerned with the cultural context in which the game jam takes place, while the Empowerment Dimension focuses on the ways in which participants are empowered to create and share their own cultural stories. The EPIC-WE Transition Tools section provides tools and methods for transitioning from one phase of the game jam to another. These tools include the Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, and Log & Pitch. The EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Methods section outlines different methods for each phase of the game jam, including methods for Experience, Play, Imagine, and Create. These methods are designed to help participants to create meaningful and culturally relevant games. Finally, the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit in Action section provides examples of the kit in action, including ways of operating the kit, as well as a pilot and playbook for the EPIC-WE game jam.

Overall, the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit is a comprehensive resource for anyone interested in organising a cultural game jam. The kit provides a step-by-step guide to the entire process, from planning and development to execution and evaluation. It

also includes a wide range of tools and methods designed to help participants create meaningful and culturally relevant games. With the help of the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit, game jam facilitators and participants can engage in game-making as culture-making to create games through and for a culture that celebrates the diversity of culture and cultural heritage while also empowering participants to create and share their own cultural game story prototypes.

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9. References

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Appendices

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10. Appendices

Appendix 10.1: Methods for EXPERIENCE

NO.	EPIC (TENTATIVE)	TITLE	ORIGINAL TITLE + Reference	DESCRIPTION (BRIEF)
1	Culturestorming		Brainstorming Design Kit, IDEO: https://www.designkit.org/methods/brainstorm.html	Resembling a traditional brainstorming activity, the participants will ideate initial and tentative games for culture ideas that incorporate values, culture, and citizenship.
2	Citizen Letters / Game Letters / Culture Letters	Love	Break Up / Love Letter Design Method Toolkit: https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/break-uplove-letter/	Rather than straightforwardly inquiring about individuals' preferences or dislikes regarding a specific perspective on culture, games, or citizenship, this method seeks to unveil their perceptions by evoking emotions derived from real-life experiences. Participants express their experiential ways of knowing and emotionality through the creative exercise of writing letters to reflect.
3	Citizens Patchwork		Collage Design Method Toolkit: https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/collage-2/	Citizens Patchwork entails affixing images or words onto a large paper to cluster ideas, personal experiences, feelings, and associations related to a specific theme or topic, here citizenship in cultural and societal contexts. Typically, collages aim to reveal a design's emotional and experiential aspects – and collectively apply verbal and symbolic language to examine and express meaning.

4	Future Worlds	Culture	Make A World Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/make-a-world/	The 'worlding' of thematic interplays between culture, values, citizenship, and games caters to visual, auditory, and kinaesthetic learners through its multi-layered interaction. This method serves a practical and enjoyable purpose by allowing players to envision the future and actively contribute to its initial realisation, thus harnessing the power of speculative futures and three-dimensional modelling of what might be desired.
5	Cultural Heritage Bloom	Lotus Blossom Design Method Toolkit: https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/lotus-blossom-2/	The concept bloom method is an explorative, creative and collective exercise, providing a structured framework for idea generation centred around a central theme. Like petals unfolding from the core, four conceptual themes emanate from the main idea. Each becomes a new central theme, generating an additional four themes.	
6	Culture Safari	Photo Safari Design Method Toolkit: https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/photo-safari/	Culture Safari involves participants capturing images of topics relevant to the project, providing distinct insights into how specific subjects and themes are perceived. Culture Safari works towards collaborative game-making in, with and for culture offers opportunities for rich visual and aesthetic inspiration in exploration and ideation processes.	
7	Creative Complexity	Rich Picture td-net – Network for	The creative complexity method visually captures implicit and explicit knowledge, aiding in understanding and decision-making	

		Transdisciplinarity Research:	for project interventions. The method centres on exploring diverse perspectives through individual and small group drawings and, afterwards, creating rich collaborative imagery emphasising the distinct elements of the game ideas.
		https://naturalsciences.ch/co-producing-knowledge-explained/methods/method_factsheets/rich_picture	
8	Empowered Participation	Roles & Responsibilities	Clarifying roles and responsibilities is crucial in guiding a team's progression from initial challenges to immersive collaboration, ensuring everyone understands their tasks.
		Hyper Island Toolbox:	This clarity minimizes confusion and enhances teamwork. In this collaborative team exercise, participants draw a table on a whiteboard – or other large surface – to identify, define, and outline roles and responsibilities and refine the list collaboratively. Through discussion and prioritization, each role's owner describes and accepts or declines identified responsibilities. Unassigned responsibilities are noted, and the session concludes with a summary.
		https://toolbox.hyperisland.com/roles-responsibilities	
9	Value Boards	Visualising values in design with mood boards	This method prompts participants to articulate and implement European values in their design projects using moodboards. Participants understand the underlying principles better by making values explicit through visual representations. In this approach, the participants utilize moodboards as a precursor
		Value Sensitive Design in Higher Education (VASE):	

		https://teachingforvaluesindesign.eu/19_visualizingvalues_moodboards.html	to prototyping, contemplating how their designs communicate with users and influence behaviours. These visual representations can meaningfully inspire the development of game prototypes.
10	Culture Walks	<p>Walkabout</p> <p>Hyper Island Toolbox: https://toolbox.hyperisland.com/walkabout</p>	This method invokes an explorative and even random approach to discovering the surroundings and spaces of the cultural heritage sites. Randomise your walking direction and observe previously unnoticed details. Document your observations through writing, photography, or drawing. In the group, share and reflect on the experience, considering what emerged and potential inspirations and actions to inform the game ideation processes.
11	Valuestorming	<p>Values clustering for developing students' value vocabularies</p> <p>Value Sensitive Design in Higher Education (VASE): https://teachingforvaluesindesign.eu/7_valuesclustering.html</p>	This activity asks participants to explore values and their conceptual synonyms, antonyms, connotations, and associations with the purpose of widening and deepening their value knowledge to emphasise values in the game's design.
12	Value Change / Culture Change	<p>How might we...?</p> <p>Design Kit, IDEO: https://www.designkit.org/</p>	This method aims to aid the game design team in translating insights into questions and turning those challenges into design opportunities. Drawing from the "How Might

nkit.org/methods/how-might-we.html

We” approach, the method’s purpose is to explore multiple solutions and frame cultural game innovation through exploring European VALUES or CULTURAL HERITAGE.

Appendix 10.2: Methods for PLAY

NO.	EPIC (TENTATIVE)	TITLE	ORIGINAL TITLE + Reference	DESCRIPTION (BRIEF)
1	Culturestorming		Brainstorming Design Kit, IDEO: https://www.designkit.org/methods/brainstorm.html	Resembling a traditional brainstorming activity, the participants will ideate initial and tentative games for cultural ideas that incorporate values, culture, and citizenship.
2	Culturewriting / Valuewriting / Gamewriting		Brainwriting innovation toolbox University of Copenhagen: https://innovationenglish.sites.ku.dk/methods/brainwriting/	In culturewriting , valuewriting or gamewriting , participants individually and silently jot down ideas, passing papers for others to build upon. This generative method produces more diverse ideas on the thematic interplays of the cultural game jams than traditional brainstorming might but is quieter and more thoughtful. It is ideal for complex ideas, emphasising diversity, empowering introverted participants, or in large groups where brainstorming is impractical.
3	6-8-5 sketching	Game	6-8-5 Sketching Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/6-8-5/	This is a brainstorming activity to aid designers in creating multiple rough ideas rapidly. Through quick and tight idea generation, the design team focuses on exploring several potential ideas - not the “best” one. The purpose of the activity is to become creative and identify as many ideas for cultural games as possible in a short period of time.

4	Sketching Games for culture	The Sketch Game Hyper Island Toolbox: https://toolbox.hyperisland.com/the-sketch-game	Collaborative drawing can aid exploration of different perspectives and thus cultural diversities. Through this approach, the participants draw their interpretations of culture, games, values, and citizenship, and collectively examine their similarities, differences, potentials, and implication.
5	Games for culture mockups	Cardboard Prototyping Method Library by This is Service Design Doing: https://www.thisiservice.com/methods/cardboard-prototyping	Games for culture mockups is a resource-effective and accessible method for exploring and testing how a game might look, appear, feel, and be experienced. These prototypes, built swiftly using inexpensive materials like paper and cardboard, facilitate easy exploration and iteration. With low entry barriers and a disposable nature, users often feel more comfortable suggesting changes during testing. The process of mockups can be crucial in concretising concepts, exploring details, and understanding strengths and weaknesses of game ideas and concepts.
6	Adverse Angles	Dark Side Design Method Toolkit: https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/dark-side/	The Adverse Angles method transforms your cultural/game-making challenge into a negative perspective, offering a fresh exploration angle. It's useful when participants seek numerous ideas by reframing design challenges negatively to encourage exposure to and exploration of different viewpoints. A vital part of the method is ensuring that the participant's positive ideas genuinely bring something new and thus foster creative outputs.

7	Decision Dash	Dot Voting Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/category/core-games/	In productive ideation and development sessions, decision dash as an approach towards voting provides a simple method to prioritise, decision-make and reach a consensus when faced with abundant ideas, concepts, and possibilities. To enact the method, the participants need a list of items to vote on, whether a wall of sticky notes or a flip chart capturing ideas. It thus follows more explorative processes and approaches, leading to numerous ideas to revisit and decide on. Participants cast their votes by placing markers next to the items they feel strongly about, typically with each participant given five votes. After tallying the votes, the prioritised list becomes the focus of discussion and decision-making. This versatile technique prioritises features, discussion topics, or strategies.
8	Citizen Empathy Mapping	Empathy Map Service Design Tools by Oblo: https://servicedesigntools.org/tools/empathy-map	The method focuses on mapping a persona or player's experiences with a game prototype, game concept or experience design, utilising the design and reflection technique of mapping experiences and affect. This activity centres around placing a fictional persona at the core, capturing their subjective thoughts, feelings, and interactions with the game. The collective exploration and discussion focus on understanding what this persona would think, feel, see, say, do, and hear concerning the game concept and interactive, experiential elements.

9	Citizen Manifesto	Manifestos on Values and Ethics Value Sensitive Design in Higher Education (VASE): https://teachingforvaluesindesign.eu/5_manifestosonvalues.html	This method aims to empower participants to articulate their values and translate them into shared team manifestos as value statements and orientations, shaping a unified approach to game design and development. The manifesto encapsulates the team's shared values, providing a foundation for interpreting them as design positions and orientations. Crafting this manifesto somewhat early during the examination and development processes is advisable, offering the collaborative groups a clear understanding of their shared design principles and approach.
10	Game Meshwork	Mashup Design Method Toolkit: https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/mash-up/	Participants will collaborate in groups to develop a game concept utilising culture and art as primary materials, aiming for a game with cultural significance. As part of the Play Phase, the group will delve into four categories integral to their version of a 'culture game.' The brainstorming method employed here is MESHWORK, emphasising the interwovenness of different elements. This approach aids in exploring the four categories of Values, Citizenship, Culture, and Games through subsequent individual and collective brainstorming and converging them in the middle, where they amalgamate into initial game ideas.
11	Games for Culture Moodspaces	Moodboard Gamestorming: https://gamestormi	A moodspace is a collaborative three-dimensional representation of emotions, experiences, and thoughts through diverse materials, images, and words – and on posters,

		ng.com/mood-board/	as material constructions, on floors, or otherwise. Participants collaborate across culture, art, values, and game-making, guided by perspectives from object-mediated communication and reflection. The goal is to collectively shape ideas, problems, or perspectives, capturing shared experiences and symbolising them through a different symbolic mode of expression. The construction concludes when participants experience their moodspace effectively communicating their shared perspectives.
12	Paper Prototyping	<p>Paper Prototyping Design Method Toolkit:</p> <p>https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/paper-prototyping-2/</p>	<p>Paper prototyping is a widely used low-fidelity method for prototyping and testing software and interfaces through interactive paper mock-ups. In this method, different interface screens are explored and hand-sketched on paper. For testing the prototype, the user usually interacts with the interface by "clicking" with their finger, and the researcher simulates computer or device operations by replacing or adding details on smaller pieces of paper. Despite its basic appearance, a paper prototype can be high-fidelity in navigational structure and features, providing valuable insights into these areas early in the design process.</p>
13	Culture Safari	<p>Photo Safari Design Method Toolkit:</p> <p>https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/photo-safari-2/</p>	<p>Visual foraging involves participants capturing images of topics relevant to the project, providing distinct insights into how specific subjects and themes are perceived. Visual foraging towards collaborative game-making in, with and for culture offers opportunities for</p>

		od-card/photo-safari/	rich visual and aesthetic inspiration in exploration and ideation processes.
14	Cultural Provotyping	<p>Provotyping</p> <p>Fuel4Design: http://www.fuel4design.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/008-IO4_FDT_PROVOTYPE.pdf</p>	<p>A provotype is a combination of the two words prototype and provocation. Generally, it is a method that aims to provoke discussions and reflection on the future – and how a given provotype tells a story about a future. The method applies materials to mediate perspectives and provoke debate. In EPIC-WE, it translates to game provotypes that become mediums for extending debates and provoking novel reflections on the thematic interplays between culture, games, citizenship, and values – and how games for culture can create new stories and/or transform existing ones.</p>
15	Rapid Prototyping	<p>Rapid Prototyping</p> <p>Design Kit, IDEO: https://www.designkit.org/methods/rapid-prototyping.html</p>	<p>Prototyping is a vital tool for game designers, allowing ideas and conceptualisations to become tangible and facilitating rapid feedback from the relevant stakeholders. Quick testing with real users helps identify impactful concepts and refine early ideas. Simple prototypes save time and enable focused testing on critical elements. Rapid prototyping aims to select promising concepts and step into an iterative process, with each iteration involving feedback integration and solution refinement. In EPIC-WE, rapid prototyping is applied as a low fidelity, quick and dirty prototyping and tinkering method to materialise, visualise, and test early ideas and concepts towards games for culture.</p>

16	Empowered Participation	Roles & Responsibilities Hyper Island Toolbox: https://toolbox.hyperisland.com/roles-responsibilities	Clarifying roles and responsibilities is crucial in guiding a team's progression from initial challenges to immersive collaboration, ensuring everyone understands their tasks. This clarity minimizes confusion and enhances teamwork. In this collaborative team exercise, participants draw a table on a whiteboard – or other large surface – to identify, define, and outline roles and responsibilities and refine the list collaboratively. Through discussion and prioritization, each role's owner describes and accepts, or declines identified responsibilities. Unassigned responsibilities are noted, and the session concludes with a summary.
17	Partial Prototyping	Rough Prototyping Service Design Tools by Obler: https://servicedesign.tools.org/tools/rough-prototyping	Rough prototypes serve to illustrate and mediate game design ideas to team members, initiating discussions about the requirements for each touchpoint, mechanism, or interaction. These prototypes, whether made from paper or pre-assembled interface elements, facilitate the visual translation of thoughts into tangible objects during co-design sessions, aiding in collective design considerations. In EPIC-WE, this approach to prototyping aims to simulate specific game design elements and components and how they might work as a fully-fledged paper/cardboard prototype.
18	Concept Convergence	Stormdraining Mitre Lab: https://itk.mitre.org/toolkit-	Contrary to brainstorming, idea convergence involves distilling an extensive collection of ideas, activities, or perspectives into a more focused and valuable set. This method brings clarity to brainstorming, brainwriting, and mind

	tools/stormdraining/	<p>mapping outcomes – or likewise, divergent ideation activities enable thoughtful prioritisation and encourages the exploration of risky ideas, enhancing the team's mental agility. It is beneficial when faced with complexity post-brainstorming, lacking direction, or needing to prioritise and focus a team's activities. While it introduces convergent thinking, a challenge may be letting go of cherished ideas.</p>
<p>19 Game Stories / Values Stories / Culture Stories</p>	<p>Storyboard Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/storyboard/</p>	<p>This method encourages players to envision an ideal future by creating a sequence of words and pictures using storyboarding. Although storyboarding is a versatile approach applicable to various topics, it is particularly potent for visioning exercises, allowing participants and players to explore and generate possibilities. Beyond depicting an ideal future, storyboarding can be employed for tasks such as describing project experiences or proposing problem-solving approaches. The facilitator of the method should acknowledge potential reservations about drawing on a large scale and emphasise that the focus is on storytelling –thus displaying a possible game for culture narrative, with images playing a supporting role. Given the time constraints, participants can use words as captions, designate an "artist" within their group, and even opt for stick figures.</p>

20	Value Boards	Visualising values in design with moodboards Value Sensitive Design in Higher Education (VASE): https://teachingforvaluesindesign.eu/19_visualizingvalues_moodboards.html	This method prompts participants to articulate and implement values in their game design projects using approaches from traditional moodboards but emphasising them as values boards. Through this process, the values underlying a game for culture, its diverse interplay of games, citizenship, and culture connecting to values, become explicit and apparent to the participants. The aim is to manifest the team's approached values in various ways, such as visual appearance and symbolic language, imageries and art. Applying values boards as a foundation for prototyping, the participants are scaffolded in exploring how their design ideas communicate, approach, and rework specific values, which can further guide and inspire the continued prototyping processes and developments.
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Appendix 10.3: Methods for IMAGINE

NO.	EPIC (TENTATIVE)	TITLE	ORIGINAL TITLE + Reference	DESCRIPTION (BRIEF)
1	Games for culture mockups	Cardboard Prototyping Method Library by This is Service Design Doing: https://www.thisis servicedesigndoing.com/methods/cardboard-prototyping	Games for culture mockups is a resource-effective and accessible method for exploring and testing how a game might look, appear, feel, and be experienced. These prototypes, built swiftly using inexpensive materials like paper and cardboard, facilitate easy exploration and iteration. With low entry barriers and a disposable nature, users often feel more comfortable suggesting changes during testing. The process of mockups can be crucial in concretising concepts, exploring details, and understanding strengths and weaknesses of game ideas and concepts.	
2	Game for Culture Declarations	Design Principles Design Kit, IDEO: https://www.designkit.org/methods/design-principles.html	As your ideas take shape, Design Principles emerge as guiding elements, akin to guidelines and team statements, ensuring consistency in iterations. These principles encapsulate the core elements of a game for culture ideas and concepts, providing integrity and structure to the game design. They often align with ideational and explorative processes and evolve throughout the design process, emphasising the importance of keeping them concise and memorable, distinct from lower-level ideas like specific colour preferences or promotional details. They are relevant for EPIC-WE in materialising guiding design	

principles and a collaborative bases for games for culture.

3	Decision Dash	<p>Dot Voting</p> <p>Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/category/core-games/</p>	<p>In productive ideation and development sessions, decision dash as an approach towards voting provides a simple method to prioritise and reach a consensus when faced with abundant ideas, concepts, and possibilities. To enact the method, the participants need a list of items to vote on, whether a wall of sticky notes or a flip chart capturing ideas. It thus follows more explorative processes and approaches, leading to numerous ideas to revisit and decide on. Participants cast their votes by placing markers next to the items they feel strongly about, typically with each participant given five votes. After tallying the votes, the prioritised list becomes the focus of discussion and decision-making. This versatile technique prioritises features, discussion topics, or strategies.</p>
4	Experience Mapping	<p>Empathy Map</p> <p>Service Design Tools by Oblo: https://servicedesigntools.org/tools/empathy-map</p>	<p>The method focuses on mapping a persona or player's experiences with a game prototype, game concept or experience design, utilising the design and reflection technique of mapping experiences and affect. This activity centres around placing a fictional persona at the core, capturing their subjective thoughts, feelings, and interactions with the game. The collective exploration and discussion focus on understanding what this persona would think, feel, see, say, do, and hear concerning the</p>

			game concept and interactive, experiential elements.
5	Games for Culture Moodspaces	Moodboard Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/mood-board/	A moodspace is a collaborative three-dimensional representation of emotions, experiences, and thoughts through diverse materials, images, and words – and on posters, as material constructions, on floors, or otherwise. Participants collaborate across culture, art, values, and game-making, guided by perspectives from object-mediated communication and reflection. The goal is to collectively shape ideas, problems, or perspectives, capturing shared experiences and symbolising them through a different symbolic mode of expression. The construction concludes when participants experience their moodspace effectively communicating their shared perspectives.
6	Paper Prototyping	Paper Prototyping Design Method Toolkit: https://toolkits.dss.cloud/design/method-card/paper-prototyping-2/	Paper prototyping is a widely used low-fidelity method for prototyping and testing software and interfaces through interactive paper mock-ups. In this method, different interface screens are explored and hand-sketched on paper. For testing the prototype, the user usually interacts with the interface by "clicking" with their finger, and the researcher simulates computer or device operations by replacing or adding details on smaller pieces of paper. Despite its basic appearance, a paper prototype can be high-fidelity in navigational structure and features, providing valuable insights into these areas early in the design process.

7	Cultural Provotyping	Provotyping Fuel4Design: http://www.fuel4design.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/008-IO4_FDT_PROVOTYPE.pdf	A provotype is a combination of the two words prototype and provocation. Generally, it is a method that aims to provoke discussions and reflection on the future – and how a given provotype tells a story about a future. The method applies materials to mediate perspectives and provoke debate. In EPIC-WE, it translates to game provotypes that become mediums for extending debates and provoking novel reflections on the thematic interplays between culture, games, citizenship, and values – and how games for culture can create new stories and/or transform existing ones.
8	Rapid Prototyping	Rapid Prototyping Design Kit, IDEO: https://www.designkit.org/methods/rapid-prototyping.html	Prototyping is a vital tool for game designers, allowing ideas and conceptualisations to become tangible and facilitating rapid feedback from the relevant stakeholders. Quick testing with real users helps identify impactful concepts and refine early ideas. Simple prototypes save time and enable focused testing on critical elements. Rapid prototyping aims to select promising concepts and step into an iterative process, with each iteration involving feedback integration and solution refinement. In EPIC-WE, rapid prototyping is applied as a low fidelity, quick and dirty prototyping and tinkering method to materialise, visualise, and test early ideas and concepts towards games for culture.
9	Empowered Participation	Roles & Responsibilities	Clarifying roles and responsibilities is crucial in guiding a team's progression from initial

		Hyper Island Toolbox: https://toolbox.hyperisland.com/roles-responsibilities	challenges to immersive collaboration, ensuring everyone understands their tasks. This clarity minimizes confusion and enhances teamwork. In this collaborative team exercise, participants draw a table on a whiteboard – or other large surface – to identify, define, and outline roles and responsibilities and refine the list collaboratively. Through discussion and prioritization, each role's owner describes and accepts or declines identified responsibilities. Unassigned responsibilities are noted, and the session concludes with a summary.
10	Partial Prototyping	Rough Prototyping Service Design Tools by Oblique: https://servicedesign.tools.org/tools/rough-prototyping	Rough prototypes serve to illustrate and mediate game design ideas to team members, initiating discussions about the requirements for each touchpoint, mechanism, or interaction. These prototypes, whether made from paper or pre-assembled interface elements, facilitate the visual translation of thoughts into tangible objects during co-design sessions, aiding in collective design considerations. In EPIC-WE, this approach to prototyping aims to simulate specific game design elements and components and how they might work as a fully-fledged paper/cardboard prototype.
11	N/A	Six Thinking Hats Untools: https://untools.co/six-thinking-hats	Sound decision-making often involves considering various perspectives to avoid overlooking crucial aspects. The Six Thinking Hats tool facilitates this by providing different lenses or perspectives. Whether used individually or in a group setting, each hat symbolizes a unique style of thinking. You can assign hats in a group to ensure a balanced

discussion or collectively explore different perspectives. In the context of EPIC-WE, this tool extends to diverse explorations and negotiations within a team, spanning game design, creativity, positivity, negativity, and core elements in citizenship, values, games, and culture.

12	Game Stories / Values Stories / Culture Stories	Storyboard Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/storyboard/	<p>This method encourages players to envision an ideal future by creating a sequence of words and pictures using storyboarding. Although storyboarding is a versatile approach applicable to various topics, it is particularly potent for visioning exercises, allowing participants and players to explore and generate possibilities. Beyond depicting an ideal future, storyboarding can be employed for tasks such as describing project experiences or proposing problem-solving approaches. The facilitator of the method should acknowledge potential reservations about drawing on a large scale and emphasise that the focus is on storytelling –thus displaying a possible game for culture narrative, with images playing a supporting role. Given the time constraints, participants can use words as captions, designate an "artist" within their group, and even opt for stick figures.</p>
13	Values Boards	Visualising values in design with moodboards	<p>This method prompts participants to articulate and implement values in their game design projects using approaches from traditional</p>

moodboards but emphasising them as values boards. Through this process, the values underlying a game for culture, its diverse interplay of games, citizenship, and culture connecting to values, become explicit and apparent to the participants. The aim is to manifest the team's approached values in various ways, such as visual appearance and symbolic language, imageries and art. Applying values boards as a foundation for prototyping, the participants are scaffolded in exploring how their design ideas communicate, approach, and rework specific values, which can further guide and inspire the continued prototyping processes and developments.

Appendix 10.4: Methods for CREATE

NO.	EPIC (TENTATIVE)	TITLE + Reference	ORIGINAL TITLE	DESCRIPTION (BRIEF)
1	Games for culture mockups	Cardboard Prototyping	Method Library by This is Service Design Doing: https://www.thisisservicedesigndoing.com/methods/cardboard-prototyping	Games for culture mockups is a resource-effective and accessible method for exploring and testing how a game might look, appear, feel, and be experienced. These prototypes, built swiftly using inexpensive materials like paper and cardboard, facilitate easy exploration and iteration. With low entry barriers and a disposable nature, users often feel more comfortable suggesting changes during testing. The process of mockups can be crucial in concretising concepts, exploring details, and understanding strengths and weaknesses of game ideas and concepts.
2	Pitch Perfect	Create a Pitch	Design Kit, IDEO: https://www.designkit.org/methods/create-a-pitch.html	Crafting a pitch is a relevant approach to communicating an idea's essence, its uniqueness, and its significance, targeting diverse audiences and stakeholders from different industries and sectors. In less than a minute, articulate the core of your game design and prototype, avoiding unnecessary details and emphasising the core elements of the game for culture – and how it connects to EPIC-WE and its foundational elements.
3	Games for Culture Decision Board	MoSCoW Design Method Toolkit:		This method is suited for prioritising features into "Must have," "Should have," "Could have," and "Would like but won't get" categories at a time when there is a tangible need to finalise the

		https://toolkits.designmethod.com/moscow/	<p>game prototype and concept. This approach aims to establish a clear hierarchy for implementation, resulting in a realistic and feasible work plan for the game design team.</p>
4	Paper Prototyping	<p>Paper Prototyping Design Method Toolkit:</p> <p>https://toolkits.designmethod.com/paper-prototyping-2/</p>	<p>Paper prototyping is a widely used low-fidelity method for prototyping and testing software and interfaces through interactive paper mock-ups. In this method, different interface screens are explored and hand-sketched on paper. For testing the prototype, the user usually interacts with the interface by "clicking" with their finger, and the researcher simulates computer or device operations by replacing or adding details on smaller pieces of paper. Despite its basic appearance, a paper prototype can be high-fidelity in navigational structure and features, providing valuable insights into these areas early in the design process.</p>
5	Human Nature/Citizens in Culture	<p>Project Pinocchio Gamestorming:</p> <p>https://gamestorming.com/product-pinocchio/</p>	<p>Imagining products, services or games as animate rather than mere tools or things, scaffolds the design team to unlock unique benefits. In this method, the aim is to transform how the participants perceive objects and concepts by personifying them. Participants craft a character with a personality and a life by delving into this imaginative exercise, encouraging storytelling and outlandish traits. This method seeks to spark innovation, as the created character's traits may inspire improvements in the games for culture – and qualify the communication and dissemination of it. The method's success relies on participants</p>

			embracing the idea that the object, the concept, or the game has a life, fostering creativity and relationality, and shaping a more relatable and valuable result.
6	Empowered Participation	Roles & Responsibilities Hyper Island Toolbox: https://toolbox.hyperisland.com/roles-responsibilities	Clarifying roles and responsibilities is crucial in guiding a team's progression from initial challenges to immersive collaboration, ensuring everyone understands their tasks. This clarity minimizes confusion and enhances teamwork. In this collaborative team exercise, participants draw a table on a whiteboard – or other large surface – to identify, define, and outline roles and responsibilities and refine the list collaboratively. Through discussion and prioritization, each role's owner describes and accepts or declines identified responsibilities. Unassigned responsibilities are noted, and the session concludes with a summary.
7	Game Stories / Values Stories / Culture Stories	Storyboard Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/storyboarding/	This method encourages players to envision an ideal future by creating a sequence of words and pictures using storyboarding. Although storyboarding is a versatile approach applicable to various topics, it is particularly potent for visioning exercises, allowing participants and players to explore and generate possibilities. Beyond depicting an ideal future, storyboarding can be employed for tasks such as describing project experiences or proposing problem-solving approaches. The facilitator of the method should acknowledge potential reservations about drawing on a large scale and emphasise that the focus is on storytelling – thus displaying

			a possible game for culture narrative, with images playing a supporting role. Given the time constraints, participants can use words as captions, designate an "artist" within their group, and even opt for stick figures.
8	RetroWall/ Citizen's Wall	<p>Storywall</p> <p>td-net – Network for Transdisciplinarity Research:</p> <p>https://naturalsciences.ch/co-producing-knowledge-explained/methods/td-net_toolbox/storywall</p>	<p>This method facilitates a retrospective examination of collaborative processes, like co-producing knowledge, by gathering individual perspectives through storytelling. Starting with a timeline on a poster, the group marks key process phases or events, fostering an exchange of their significance. This method contrasts diverse viewpoints, promoting mutual understanding as different group members may perceive and emphasize elements differently. Typically done post-process, i.e., late in the Create phase, the method involves explaining individual perceptions, bridging thought-styles, and culminates in a poster capturing the group's collective perspective on the most crucial elements of the shared story.</p>
9	Values Boards	<p>Visualising values in design with moodboards</p> <p>Value Sensitive Design in Higher Education (VASE):</p> <p>https://teachingforvaluesindesign.eu/19_visualizing</p>	<p>This method prompts participants to articulate and implement values in their game design projects using approaches from traditional moodboards but emphasising them as values boards. Through this process, the values underlying a game for culture, its diverse interplay of games, citizenship, and culture connecting to values, become explicit and apparent to the participants. The aim is to manifest the team's approached values in various ways, such as visual appearance and</p>

		aluesmoodboards.html	<p>symbolic language, imageries and art. Applying values boards as a foundation for prototyping, the participants are scaffolded in exploring how their design ideas communicate, approach, and rework specific values, which can further guide and inspire the continued prototyping processes and developments.</p>
10	Plaque Expo	<p>Poster Session</p> <p>Gamestorming: https://gamestorming.com/poster-session/</p>	<p>A plaque exposition – like a poster session format – accelerates idea and concept presentation by having participants summarize their ideas and concepts with images, fostering efficient communication without lengthy explanations.</p> <p>Participants create self-explanatory visual posters within 20 minutes, focusing on the "Before and After," "System," and "Process" aspects of their ideas and how they become games for culture absorbing, rekindling, transforming, or addressing culture, citizenship, and values in games. Posters are then displayed gallery-style, allowing attendees to circulate and absorb information without elaborate presentations.</p> <p>This method draws inspiration from academic poster sessions, promoting informal, conversational idea sharing.</p>

Appendix 10.6: Methods Guide Overview – Local CGJ

ReadMe

The EPIC-WE Methods Guide is a collection of diverse methods and approaches to bring together art, games, culture, and values in a rapid game-making process.

During the different phases of the Cultural Game Jam, 1) Experience, 2) Play, 3) Imagine, and 4) Create, the development team should choose methods that correspond with the goals and needs of the group. However, some methods are obligatory, while others are strongly encouraged.

Each method card contains a general description, brief how-to guide, proposed reflection questions, repeated materials, outcomes, and links to use the method. Finally, a QR code is provided for each method, linking to its inspiration and more details and help.

Please ask the facilitators or other participants any questions if you need help choosing, getting it started, or anything else.

START EXPERIENCE

Culturstorming

How

1. Frame a question grounded in culture and the chosen artwork
2. Individually brainstorm 5 ideas in 3 minutes in written form - 1 idea per Post-It
3. Group ideas into categories or themes.
4. In the group, decide on your favourite ideas for innovative games through and for culture.

What
Pen, post-its, and papers.

Outcome
A number of cultural ideas to move forward with.

Reflect

1. What cultural experience do we want the player to have?
2. How do we use culture as material for a game?
3. How can the game capture the essence of the chosen cultural heritage?

Use
Early in the "Experience" phase.

Reference

20-40 minutes

Experience

Culture

Valuestorming

How

1. Put your chosen European value in the middle
2. Individually brainstorm in 5 minutes on post-its notes conceptual synonyms, antonyms, connotations, and associations
3. Group notes into categories or themes.
4. In the group, decide on a favourite combination of notes for inspiring games for culture with value

What
Pen, post-its, and papers

Outcome
A number of value ideas to move forward with.

Reflect

1. What values would we like the player to experience? Why?
2. What is essential to the value we are working with? How do we make the value powerful?
3. What is the relationship between the value in the game and how that value is experienced in culture or society?

Use
Early in the "Experience" phase.

Reference

20-40 minutes

Experience

Values

Valuestorming

How

1. Put your chosen European value in the middle
2. Individually brainstorm in 5 minutes on post-its notes conceptual synonyms, antonyms, connotations, and associations
3. Group notes into categories or themes.
4. In the group, decide on a favourite combination of notes for inspiring games for culture with value

What
Pen, post-its, and papers

Outcome
A number of value ideas to move forward with.

Reflect

1. What values would we like the player to experience? Why?
2. What is essential to the value we are working with? How do we make the value powerful?
3. What is the relationship between the value in the game and how that value is experienced in culture or society?

Use
Early in the "Experience" phase.

Reference

30-45 minutes

Experience

Citizenship

Citizen Love Letters

How

1. Write a love letter for a citizenship perspective about culture
2. Gather your game design team, go through all the letters and find commonalities between them to see what elements influence you the most.

What
Pen and paper

Outcome
Experiential and emotional perspectives to enhance game ideas

Reflect

1. How can our game create a cultural experience that citizens will love?
2. What emotions do citizens have in culture now? And how does our game for culture change it?
3. Does citizenship have special properties that will influence our game?

Use
During the "Experience" phase to examine shared perspectives

Reference

30-45 minutes

Experience

Citizenship

Game Love Letters

How

1. Write a love letter for a game perspective about games
2. Gather your game design team, go through all the letters and find commonalities between them to see what elements influence you the most.

What
Pen and paper

Outcome
Experiential and emotional perspectives to enhance game ideas

Reflect

1. Why do players fall in love with the game? How does it relate to culture and value?
2. What is it about the game that makes it feel powerful and special?
3. What cultural pleasure or value does the game have?
4. How is the game innovative? What is novel, surprising or strange?

Use
During the "Experience" phase to examine shared perspectives

Reference

30-45 minutes

Experience

Games

Culture Love Letters

How

1. Write a love letter for a game perspective about culture
2. Gather your game design team, go through all the letters and find commonalities between them to see what elements influence you the most.

What
Pen and paper

Outcome
Experiential and emotional perspectives to enhance game ideas

Reflect

1. What elements of culture make you fall in love? How can they be incorporated into a game?
2. What emotions and experiences does culture give rise to? How can we capture them with a game?
3. How can we use culture to create experiences and interactions that are innovative and new in games?

Use
During the "Experience" phase to examine shared perspectives

Reference

30-45 minutes

Experience

Culture

Culture Safari

How

1. Explore the collection space by asking: What atmospheres, stories, and themes come to life in this space?
2. Take photos of what excites you.
3. Collect the group's photos and compare them. Tell stories about your photos, collect insights, and identify common threads.

What
Camera and post-its.

Outcome
Exploring and understanding the cultural context.

Reflect

1. How does the game actively use the collection as game-making material?
2. How does the game respond to culture and cultural heritage?
3. How can the game become part of the atmosphere, stories and themes?

Use
When you need knowledge about inspiration from the cultural context.

Reference

20-35 minutes

All Phases

Citizenship

Empowered Participation

How

1. Draw a grid on paper
2. In the vertical columns (responsibility), write "What I think" and "What others think."
3. In the horizontal rows (roles), write the four roles: artist, designer, collaborator, and storyteller.
4. Define your roles, clarify your own AND your teammates' responsibilities, and discuss each role.

What
Pen and paper

Outcome
Shared understanding of roles and responsibilities

Reflect

1. How can we be an epic team for this game? How can we make the most of our competencies?
2. How do we ensure that we work together and only the roles into a single game?
3. How should we feel, collaborate and be together as a team? What is our ambition?

Use
Both early and recurrent to define, explore, and agree on roles and responsibilities

Reference

30-45 minutes

Experience

Values

Empowered Participation

How

1. Start by revisiting earlier activities and write 3-5 value statements each.
2. Rephrase them as questions by adding "How might we...?"
3. View your questions and ask if they allow for many different ideas or solutions or need to be broadened.
4. A good "How might we..." question is clear and inspires new and alternate problems and ideas for solutions.

What
Value statements, paper, pens, post-its.

Outcome
A number of questions to extend ideation.

Reflect

1. How can we make games based on values? What important questions would such a game be able to answer?
2. What question will create a truly new experience or meaningful cultural change for young people? How can we work with value to achieve that?

Use
It is best used after initial idea generation processes.

Reference

30-45 minutes

Experience

Values

<h3>Culture Change</h3> <p>This method aims to aid the game design team in translating insights into questions and turning those challenges into design opportunities. Drawing from the "How Might We" approach, the method's purpose is to explore multiple solutions and frame cultural game innovation through exploring CULTURAL HERITAGE.</p> <p>30-45 minutes</p> <p>Experience Culture</p>				
<h3>Culture Collage</h3> <p>How</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prepare by clarifying your cultural emphasis or interest. 2. Collect materials from all available sources - online, physical, your own creations, etc. 3. Organise and refine the materials - in a physical or digital space - to depict a cultural mood or atmosphere you want the game to convey. 4. Present and discuss its influence on potential game design with the team. <p>What Paper, glue, images, magazines, stock photos, etc.</p> <p>Outcome A collage to guide the cultural aspects of game design.</p> <p>Use After choosing a game design idea to enrich it.</p> <p>Reflect</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is the cultural atmosphere of our game? How can we use artistic content to communicate and deepen the atmosphere? 2. What is the special cultural feeling of our game? 3. How does our game make cultural heritage come alive? <p>Reference</p> </p>				
<h3>6-8-5 Game Sketching</h3> <p>This is a brainstorming activity to aid designers in creating multiple rough ideas rapidly. Through quick and tight idea generation, the design team focuses on exploring several potential ideas - not the "best" one. The purpose of the activity is to become creative and identify as many ideas for cultural games as possible in a short period of time.</p> <p>20 minutes</p> <p>Play Values</p>				
<h3>Citizen Manifestos</h3> <p>How</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Explore the teams' chosen value through its synonyms, antonyms, denotations, and connotations. 2. Discuss how it might influence your game design and development. 3. Translate the elaborated values into shared design principles and manifestos that emphasise your design team's mutual understanding and accentuate civic voices. <p>What Pen, paper, post-its, glue, etc.</p> <p>Outcome Shared understandings to guide game design and accentuate civic voices.</p> <p>Use After choosing values and the first processes of game idea exploration.</p> <p>Reflect</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do we create a game that makes culture and cultural heritage meaningful to young people like us? 2. How do we create a game that empowers us as citizens in culture? 3. How could we make cultural heritage exciting to young people like us? 4. What do we want from culture and cultural heritage? <p>Reference</p> </p>				

<h3>Future Culture Worlds</h3> <p>The 'worlding' of thematic interplays between culture, values, citizenship, and games caters to visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners through its multi-layered interaction. This method serves a practical purpose by allowing players to envision the future and actively contribute to its initial realisation, thus harnessing the power of speculative futures and three-dimensional modelling of what might be desired.</p> <p>45-75 minutes</p> <p>Play Culture</p>				
<h3>Game for Culture Declarations</h3> <p>How</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Revisit your game ideas and themes. Reflect on the core principles underpinning these. Frame these as positive statements that tell you how and what to design. Review your culture declarations and ensure they cover your solution's key aspects. Be ready to revise them as you begin prototyping and testing your ideas. <p>What Pens, post-its, paper</p> <p>Outcome Several declarations - principles - to guide game design</p> <p>Use After finding game ideas and themes, before prototyping</p> <p>Reference</p>				
<h3>Cultural Prototyping</h3> <p>A prototype is a combination of the two words prototype and provocation. Generally, it is a method that aims to provoke discussions and reflection on the future - and how a given provotype tells a story about a future. The method aims to create game prototypes to extend debates and provoke novel reflections on the thematic interplays between culture, games, citizenship, and values - and how games for culture can create new stories and/or transform existing ones.</p> <p>45-120 minutes</p> <p>Imagine Games</p>				
<h3>Rough Mockup</h3> <p>How</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The rough mockup helps explain and decide on game ideas. Create a game mockup - built with paper or existing interface elements (e.g., wireframe/UI kits, game engine). Use mockup(s) to visualise ideas - and consider design paths. <p>What Interface elements, game engine, paper, etc.</p> <p>Outcome A tangible mockup to discuss and decide with.</p> <p>Use When a tangible and visual element is needed for decisions and iterations.</p> <p>Reference</p>	<h1>CREATE</h1>			

<h3>Playable Prototypes</h3> <p>This approach aims to translate ideas and concepts into a playable prototype imbued by the different roles' responsibilities and the categories of GAMES, CULTURE, VALUES, and CITIZENSHIP.</p> <p>A playable prototype can be digital, analogue, or hybrid - on paper, cardboard, browsers, or elsewhere. The purpose is here to transition from mockups to interactive games: by physical or digital materials.</p> <p>2-6 hours</p> <p>Create Culture</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>				
<h3>Pitching Games for Culture</h3> <p>How</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. With your game idea and prototype created - or soon to be - it's time to create a pitch. 2. Use the team's Game Log 1-4 to create a compelling pitch. 3. In 1-3 minutes, you want to tell the essence of the game: its artistic, narrative, technical, and design choices; its use and change of culture, values, and citizenship. <p>Reflect</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do you make others fall in love with your game? What is the powerful cultural story or argument for your game? 2. How have you worked with cultural heritage and values to create a powerful or innovative game? 3. How does your game make a difference? Why is it important or empowering? <p>What Presentation tool or format</p> <p>Outcome Brief presentations of game for culture idea and prototype.</p> <p>Use When ready to communicate a game prototype; combine with plaque</p> <p>Reference</p> Games</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>				
<h3>Citizens in Culture</h3> <p>This method aims to transform how the participants perceive objects and concepts by personifying them. Participants craft a character with a personality and a life by delving into this imaginative exercise, encouraging storytelling and outlandish traits. This method seeks to spark innovation, as the created character's traits may inspire improvements in the games for culture - and qualify the communication and dissemination of it.</p> <p>45-60 minutes</p> <p>Create Citizenship</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>				
<h2>Plaque Expo</h2> <p>How</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Plaque EXPO is vital in submitting and showcasing your game prototype - telling and showing how the game idea, concept, and prototype came together and how your game is a <i>game for culture</i>. 2. Your game's plaque is your game's submission page (frontpage) 3. Go to your team's submission front page and ensure the content is clear and aesthetically satisfactory and all elements are there. 4. Let the game jam facilitators know when the plaque is ready to be printed for the EXPO (the plaque can also be shown on a screen using a laptop) 5. The plaque should be featured next to your game for culture. <p>What Paper, cardboard, pens, markers, etc.</p> <p>Outcome A 'Plaque' to display the key elements of the game idea and prototype.</p> <p>Use At the end of the 'Create' to support documentation and EXPO</p> <p>Reference</p> <p>END</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>				

Appendix 10.7: Methods Guide Display – Local CGJ

The cover of the EPIC-WE Methods Guide features a teal background. At the top left is the European Union flag logo with the text "Funded by the European Union". The title "EPIC-WE METHODS GUIDE" is centered in large white letters. Below the title is the EPIC-WE logo, a colorful knot-like symbol. At the bottom right, there is a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license icon.

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EPIC-WE METHODS GUIDE

CC BY

START

ReadMe

The EPIC-WE Methods Guide is a collection of diverse methods and approaches to bring together art, games, culture, and values in a rapid game-making process.

During the different phases of the Cultural Game Jam, 1) Experience, 2) Play, 3) Imagine, and 4) Create, the development team should choose methods that correspond with the goals and needs of the group. However, some methods are obligatory, while others are strongly encouraged.

Each method card contains a general description, brief how-to guide, proposed reflection questions, expected materials, outcomes, and when to use the method. Finally, a QR code is provided for each method, linking to its inspiration and more details and help.

Please ask the facilitators or other participants any questions if you need help choosing, getting it started, or anything else.

EXPERIENCE

Culturestorming

Resembling a traditional brainstorming activity, the participants will ideate initial and tentative games for culture ideas that incorporate values, culture and citizenship. In *culturestorming*, the purpose is to generate novel ideas about culture and cultural heritage and its perspectives and themes to enrich the cultural understanding and its relation to creating games.

20-40 minutes

Culturestorming

How

1. Frame a question grounded in culture and the chosen artwork
2. Individually brainstorm 5 ideas in 3 minutes in written form - 1 idea per Post-it.
3. Group ideas into categories or themes.
4. In the group, decide on your favourite ideas for innovative games through and for culture.

What

Pen, post-its, and papers.

Outcome

A number of cultural ideas to move forward with.

Reflect

1. What cultural experience do we want the player to have?
2. How do we use culture as material for a game?
3. How can the game capture the essence of the chosen cultural heritage?

Use

Early in the "Experience" phase.

Reference

Valuestorming

This activity asks participants to explore values and their conceptual synonyms, antonyms, connotations, and associations with the purpose of widening and deepening their value knowledge to emphasise values in the game's design.

20-40 minutes

Valuestorming

How

1. Put your chosen European value in the middle
2. Individually brainstorm in 5 minutes on post-it notes conceptual synonyms, antonyms, connotations, and associations
3. Group notes into categories or themes.
4. In the group, decide on a favourite constellation of notes for imbuing games for culture with value

What

Pen, post-its, and papers

Outcome

A number of value ideas to move forward with.

Reflect

1. What values would we like the player to experience? Why?
2. What is essential to the value we are working with? How do we make the value powerful?
3. What is the relationship between the value in the game and how that value is experienced in culture or society?

Use

Early in the "Experience" phase.

Reference

Citizen Love Letters

Rather than straightforwardly inquiring about individuals' preferences or dislikes regarding a specific perspective on culture, values, games, or citizenship, this method seeks to unveil their perceptions by evoking emotions derived from real-life experiences. Participants express their feelings through the creative exercise of writing letters to reflect creatively - and in the Citizen Love Letters about **CITIZENSHIP** in relation to games, values, and culture.

30-45 minutes

Citizen Love Letters

How

1. Write a love letter for a citizenship perspective about games for/through culture that you are currently in love with.
2. Gather your game design team, go through all the letters and find commonalities between them to see what elements influence you the most.

Reflect

1. How can our game create a cultural experience that citizens will love?
2. What emotions do citizens have in culture now? And how does our game for culture change it?
3. Does citizenship have special properties that will influence our game?

What

Pen and paper

Outcome

Experiential and emotional perspectives to enhance game ideas

Use

During the "Experience" phase to examine shared perspectives

Reference

Game Love Letters

Rather than straightforwardly inquiring about individuals' preferences or dislikes regarding a specific perspective on culture, values, games, or citizenship, this method seeks to unveil their perceptions by evoking emotions derived from real-life experiences. Participants express their feelings through the creative exercise of writing letters to reflect creatively - and in the Game Love Letters about **GAMES** in relation to citizenship, values, and culture.

30-45 minutes

Game Love Letters

How

1. Write a love letter for a game perspective about games for/through culture that you are currently in love with.
2. Gather your game design team, go through all the letters and find commonalities between them to see what elements influence you the most.

Reflect

1. Why do players fall in love with the game? How does it relate to culture and value?
2. What is it about the game that makes it feel powerful and special?
3. What cultural pleasure or value does the game have?
4. How is the game innovative? What is novel, surprising or strange?

What

Pen and paper

Outcome

Experiential and emotional perspectives to enhance game ideas

Use

During the "Experience" phase to examine shared perspectives

Reference

Culture Love Letters

Rather than straightforwardly inquiring about individuals' preferences or dislikes regarding a specific perspective on culture, values, games, or citizenship, this method seeks to unveil their perceptions by evoking emotions derived from real-life experiences. Participants express their feelings through the creative exercise of writing letters to reflect creatively - and in the Game Love Letters about **CULTURE** in relation to citizenship, values, and games.

30-45 minutes

Culture Love Letters

How

1. Write a love letter for a game perspective about culture for/through culture that you are currently in love with.
2. Gather your game design team, go through all the letters and find commonalities between them to see what elements influence you the most.

Reflect

1. What elements of culture make you fall in love? How can they be incorporated into a game?
2. What emotions and experiences does culture give rise to? How can we capture them with a game?
3. How can we use culture to create experiences and interactions that are innovative and new in games?

What

Pen and paper

Outcome

Experiential and emotional perspectives to enhance game ideas

Use

During the "Experience" phase to examine shared perspectives

Reference

Culture Safari

This activity involves participants capturing images of topics relevant to the project, providing distinct insights into how specific subjects and themes are perceived. Culture Safari towards collaborative game-making in, with and for culture offers opportunities for rich visual and aesthetic inspiration from cultural heritage in exploration and ideation processes.

30-45 minutes

Culture Safari

How

1. Explore the collection space by asking: What atmospheres, stories, and themes come to life in this space?
2. Take photos of what excites you.
3. Collect the groups' photos and compare them. Tell stories about your photos, collect insights, and identify common threads.

Reflect

1. How does the game actively use the collection as game-making material?
2. How does the game respond to culture and cultural heritage?
3. How can the game become part of the atmosphere, stories and themes?

What

Cameras and post-its.

Outcome

Exploring and understanding the cultural context.

Use

When you need knowledge about/inspiration from the cultural context.

Reference

Empowered Participation

Clarifying roles and responsibilities is crucial in guiding a team's progression from initial challenges to immersive collaboration, ensuring everyone understands their tasks.

This method aims to explore and provide clarity to minimise confusion about roles and responsibilities and enhance teamwork.

20-35 minutes

Value Change

This method aims to aid the game design team in translating insights into questions and turning those challenges into design opportunities.

Drawing from the "How Might We" approach, the method's purpose is to explore multiple solutions and frame cultural game innovation through exploring **European VALUES**.

30-45 minutes

Empowered Participation

How

1. Draw a grid on paper
2. In the vertical columns (responsibility), write "What I think" and "What others think."
3. In the horizontal rows (roles), write the four roles: artist, designer, craftsperson, and storyteller.
4. Define your roles, clarify your own AND your teammates' responsibilities, and discuss each role.

What

Pen and paper

Outcome

Shared understanding of roles and responsibilities

Reflect

1. How can we be an epic team for this game? How can we make the most of our competencies?
2. How do we ensure that we work together and unify the roles into a single game?
3. How should we feel, collaborate and be together as a team? What is our ambition?

Use

Both early and recurrent to define, explore, and agree on roles and responsibilities

Reference

Value Change

How

1. Start by revisiting earlier activities and write 3-5 **value** statements each.
2. Rephrase them as questions by adding, "How might we...?"
3. View your questions and ask if they allow for many different ideas or solutions or need to be broadened.
4. A good How might we ...? question is clear and inspires new and alternate problems and ideas for solutions.

What

Value statements, paper, pens, post-its.

Outcome

A number of questions to extend ideation.

Reflect

1. How can we make games based on values? What important questions would such a game be able to answer?
2. What question will create a truly new experience or meaningful cultural change for young people? How can we work with value to achieve that?

Use

It is best used after initial idea generation processes.

Reference

Culture Change

This method aims to aid the game design team in translating insights into questions and turning those challenges into design opportunities. Drawing from the “How Might We” approach, the method’s purpose is to explore multiple solutions and frame cultural game innovation through exploring **CULTURAL HERITAGE**.

30-45 minutes

Experience

Culture

Culture Change

How

1. Start by revisiting earlier activities and write 3-5 **culture** statements each.
2. Rephrase them as questions by adding, “How might we...?”
3. View your question and ask if they allow for various solutions or need to be broader.
4. A good How might we ...? question is clear and inspires new and alternate problems and ideas for solutions.

What

Value statements, paper, pens, post-its.

Outcome

A number of questions to extend ideation.

Reflect

1. How can we use cultural heritage to create games that make a difference to people, create cultural change or make the world better? What is the question such a game would be the answer to?
2. How can we create cultural connections between young people and cultural heritage? What are the current problems? How can your game help?

Use

It is best used after initial idea generation processes.

Reference

Culture Collage

A collage is a visual representation of emotions, experiences, and thoughts through diverse materials, images, and words – and on posters, as material constructions, on floors, or otherwise.

The goal is to individually and collectively shape ideas, problems, or perspectives on **CULTURE**, capturing shared experiences and symbolising them through a different symbolic mode of expression.

30-45 minutes

Play

Culture

Culture Collage

How

1. Prepare by clarifying your **cultural** emphasis or interest.
2. Collect materials from all available sources - online, physical, your own creations, etc.
3. Organise and refine the materials - in a physical or digital space - to depict a cultural mood or atmosphere you want the game to convey
4. Present and discuss its influence on potential game design with the team

Reflect

1. What is the cultural atmosphere of our game? How can we use artistic content to communicate and deepen the atmosphere?
2. What is the special cultural feeling of our game?
3. How does our game make cultural heritage come alive?

What

Paper, glue, images, magazines, stock photo, etc.

Outcome

A collage to guide the cultural aspects of game design.

Use

After choosing a game design idea to enrich it.

Reference

Value Collage

A collage is a visual representation of emotions, experiences, and thoughts through diverse materials, images, and words – and on posters, as material constructions, on floors, or otherwise.

The goal is to individually and collectively shape ideas, problems, or perspectives on **VALUES**, capturing shared experiences and symbolising them through a different symbolic mode of expression.

30-45 minutes

Value Collage

How

1. Prepare by clarifying your **value** emphasis or interest.
2. Collect materials from all available sources - online, physical, your own creations, etc.
3. Organise and refine the materials - in a physical or digital space - to depict a cultural mood or atmosphere you want the game to convey
4. Present and discuss its influence on potential game design with the team

Reflect

1. How does our game for culture communicate values without using words?
2. How are values visible in the interaction, aesthetics, story and game world?
3. Is it visible also in the code/craft?

What

Paper, glue, images, magazines, stock photo, etc.

Outcome

A collage to guide the value aspects of game design.

Use

After choosing a game design idea to enrich it.

Reference

Game Collage

A collage is a visual representation of emotions, experiences, and thoughts through diverse materials, images, and words – and on posters, as material constructions, on floors, or otherwise.

The goal is to individually and collectively shape ideas, problems, or perspectives on **GAMES**, capturing shared experiences and symbolising them through a different symbolic mode of expression.

30-45 minutes

Game Collage

How

1. Prepare by clarifying your **game design** idea or interest.
2. Collect materials from all available sources - online, physical, your own creations, etc.
3. Organise and refine the materials - in a physical or digital space - to depict a cultural mood or atmosphere you want the game to convey
4. Present and discuss its influence on potential game design with the team

Reflect

1. How does our game look? What sets it apart from other games and as a cultural game world?
2. What can players look, see, do, be? How can players experience culture and cultural heritage in the game?

What

Paper, glue, images, magazines, stock photos, etc.

Outcome

A collage to guide the gameworld aspects of game design.

Use

After choosing a game design idea to enrich it.

Reference

6-8-5 Game Sketching

This is a brainstorming activity to aid designers in creating multiple rough ideas rapidly. Through quick and tight idea generation, the design team focuses on exploring several potential ideas - not the "best" one. The purpose of the activity is to become creative and identify as many ideas for cultural games as possible in a short period of time.

20 minutes

6-8-5 Game Sketching

How

1. Draw a piece of paper into a grid of 8 boxes for each participant.
2. The goal is to generate 6-8 rough games for/through culture ideas in 5 minutes.
3. When the time is up, discuss the team's ideas and decide on the most interesting ones - and if there is time, do another round.

Reflect

1. What ideas hold the biggest potential? What makes it unique?
2. What ideas use cultural heritage in the most surprising ways? In the most elegant ways? In juicy ways?
3. What ideas use culture and value in strange ways that will make players talk about them excitingly?

What

Pens and papers, post-its.

Outcome

Multiple novel game ideas.

Use

Early in the 'Play' phase - or again later if more ideas are needed.

Reference

Game Meshwork

Participants will collaborate in groups to develop a game concept utilising culture, art, and values as primary materials, aiming for a game with cultural significance.

This approach aids in exploring the four categories of Values, Citizenship, Culture, and Games through subsequent individual and collective brainstorms and converging them in the middle, where they turn into initial games for culture ideas.

1 hour

Game Meshwork

How

1. Draw a large 2x2 table with four equal squares (values, citizenship, culture, game ideas).
2. Retrieve 2 colours of Post-it notes: Round 1 and Round 2.
3. Perform a triple-brainstorm of values, citizenship, and culture - each 7 minutes.
4. Combine ideas from the first three squares into individual game ideas (7 minutes), and afterwards, collective game idea brainstorming (13 minutes) towards shared and connected ideas.

Reflect

1. How do we combine elements from all squares in meaningful, surprising, unique or elegant ways? How is our game showing connections that are deep?
2. How is our game, not a superficial game? What can we do to enhance all squares?

What

Paper, pens, post-its, view of the culture/art

Outcome

Games for culture ideas that combine values, citizenship, and culture

Use

Early in the 'Play' phase to examine and connect the categories.

Reference

Citizen Manifestos

This method empowers participants to articulate their values and translate them into shared team manifestos as value statements and orientations, shaping a unified approach to game design and development.

The purpose is to offer the collaborative groups a clear understanding of their shared design principles and approach.

20-40 minutes

Citizen Manifestos

How

1. Explore the teams' chosen value through its synonyms, antonyms, denotations, and connotations.
2. Discuss how it might influence your game design and development.
3. Translate the elaborated values into shared design principles and manifestos that emphasise your design team's mutual understanding.

What

Pen, paper, post-its, glue, etc.

Outcome

Shared understandings to guide game design and accentuate civic voices.

Use

After choosing values and the first processes of game idea exploration

Reference

Concept Convergence

Contrary to brainstorming, concept convergence involves distilling an extensive collection of ideas, activities, or perspectives into a more focused and valuable set.

It is beneficial when faced with complexity post-brainstorming, lacking direction, or needing to prioritise and focus a team's activities.

30-45 minutes

Concept Convergence

How

1. Gather a collection of ideas and design thoughts created during ideation activities.
2. Remove ideas (and post-its) - and remove them liberally with no hard feelings. All is fair game.
3. Discuss the ideas and concepts left and try to talk them through, elaborate on them, and explore why they matter to create games for culture.

What

Earlier brainstorms, post-its, pens, erasers, paper

Outcome

A set of focused and rich ideas about game for culture

Reflect

1. What is the most innovative or powerful theme and purpose? What ideas support this best?
2. What ideas make the most use of culture, cultural heritage and values? Are they empowering?
3. What ideas have dimensions (art, story, design, craft) that reinforce each other and work seamlessly together?

Use

When the design team needs to distill many ideas into a few.

Reference

Storyboard

This method encourages players to envision an ideal future by creating a sequence of words and pictures using storyboarding.

It is particularly relevant in visioning game ideas, stories, and aesthetics, allowing participants and players to explore and generate possibilities for different approaches towards creating a game for culture.

1 hour

Storyboard

How

1. In a slide deck or with pen and paper, depict individual scenes, sequences, and moments using plain text and arrows.
2. Create simple drawings and sketch scene sequences that show interactions between the player and the game.
3. Write brief explanations to elaborate on each scene.
4. Elaborate, iterate, refine.

What

A slide-maker, pens, papers, creative materials.

Outcome

Combines visual and creative thinking with structure to describe a game idea/concept.

Use

When examining new game ideas, game sequences, or for visual representation.

Reference

Future Culture Worlds

The 'worlding' of thematic interplays between culture, values, citizenship, and games caters to visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners through its multi-layered interaction. This method serves a practical purpose by allowing players to envision the future and actively contribute to its initial realisation, thus harnessing the power of speculative futures and three-dimensional modelling of what might be desired.

45-75 minutes

Future Culture Worlds

How

1. The aim is for each participant to create a future cultural world and its attributes, which can include people, scenes, buildings, values, culture, etc.
2. Begin with stating a shared vision to make it into a three-dimensional world.
3. Use 20–30 minutes to brainstorm the attributes of the world and physically create it using art supplies.
4. Showcase the worlds in the team - and document any recurring themes or parallel features.

Reflect

1. What is the secret purpose? Why are you doing this? Why does it matter?
2. Will culture look different in the future if your game is realised? How?
3. Will young people's connections to culture, cultural heritage and values look different in the future? Why?

What

Markers, post-its, wire, clay, images, tape - any art supplies.

Outcome

Visualisation of the world, atmosphere, feel of the game.

Use

To extend, enrich a game idea and concept.

Reference

Game for Culture Declarations

As your ideas take shape, design principles - or game for culture declarations - emerge as guiding elements, akin to guidelines and team statements, ensuring consistency in iterations.

Framing the core elements of the 'game for culture' ideas and concepts, they provide structure to the game design. They often align with ideational processes and evolve throughout the design process, emphasising the importance of keeping them concise and distinct from specifics like colour preferences or technological details.

45-60 minutes

Game for Culture Declarations

How

1. Revisit your game ideas and themes.
2. Reflect on the core principles underpinning those.
3. Frame these as positive statements that tell you how and what to design.
4. Review your culture declarations and ensure they cover your solution's key aspects.
5. Be ready to revise them as you begin prototyping and testing your ideas.

Reflect

1. What principles will ensure we create a game that is empowering to the player and a game that makes a difference in culture?
2. What principles will ensure we create a game that is a cultural world and a game that uses value and cultural heritage in non-superficial ways?

What

Pens, post-its, paper

Outcome

Several declarations - principles - to guide game design

Use

After finding game ideas and themes; before prototyping

Reference

Decision Dash

In productive ideation and development sessions, decision dash as an approach towards voting provides a simple method to prioritise, decision-make and reach a consensus when faced with abundant ideas, concepts, and possibilities.

The purpose of this technique is to prioritise features, discussion topics, or strategies.

15-20 minutes

Decision Dash

How

1. In any exploration process, you may have too many ideas.
2. Collect your ideas - post-its, collages, paper brainstorms, etc.
3. Cast votes by placing a dot next to the idea you feel most strongly about (individual); 4-5 votes each.
4. Count the votes and rank the ideas into a prioritised list for game design decision-making.

Reflect

1. What does the best idea or the best decision look like?
2. How do we ensure the decision enforces the game's theme, purpose and power?
3. What are the voting criteria?
4. Could we combine (best vote) ideas rather than throw them away?

What

Earlier materials + pens or stickers.

Outcome

A prioritised list of ideas to discuss and design from.

Use

When you have too many ideas and must prioritise.

Reference

Citizen Experience Mapping

The method focuses on mapping a persona or player's experiences with a game prototype, game concept or experience design, utilising the design and reflection technique of mapping experiences and affect.

The collective exploration and discussion focus on understanding what this persona would think, feel, see, say, do, and hear concerning the game concept and interactive, experiential elements

25-30 minutes

Citizen Experience Mapping

How

1. In teams, draw a circle on paper to represent a citizen player persona.
2. Divide the circle into sections, representing that persona's sensory experience: what they might see, hear, feel, think, do, and say.
3. Describe the persona's experience from their point of view - and discuss its influence on game design.

Reflect

1. What emotions would we like the player to experience? Why?
2. What sensory experience would we like the game to give? Why?
3. How would we like our players to react to the game? Why?
4. How would we like our player to think and reflect? Why?
5. How does this change the player, the game or the world?

What

Pen, paper, markers, post-its.

Outcome

Insight in the needs and desires of the persona to strengthen game design.

Use

When experiential insights are needed.

Reference

Cultural Provotyping

A provotype is a combination of the two words prototype and provocation. Generally, it is a method that aims to provoke discussions and reflection on the future – and how a given provotype tells a story about a future.

The method aims to create game provotypes to extend debates and provoke novel reflections on the thematic interplays between culture, games, citizenship, and values – and how games for culture can create new stories and/or transform existing ones.

45-120 minutes

Rapid Mockup

Rapid prototyping aims to select promising concepts and step into an iterative process, with each iteration involving feedback integration and solution refinement. Here, rapid prototyping is applied as a low fidelity, quick and dirty prototyping and tinkering method to materialise, visualise, and test early ideas and concepts towards games for culture.

45-120 minutes

Cultural Provotyping

How

1. Revisit your game idea and the story you want to tell.
2. Discuss what game type you want to create - and how it might tell your story.
3. Sketch a prototype to represent your idea and story - and to provoke cultural debate.

Reflect

1. What problem is the game trying to raise? How?
2. How does the game spark debate around your chosen cultural heritage and/or value?
3. How does the game call for activism, resistance, or
4. What does the game judge (players, culture, world)? And why does it provoke?

What

Pen, paper, any materials needed.

Outcome

A provocative prototype sketch to debate culture.

Use

When you need to sharpen and re-wild your game idea and story.

Reference

Rapid Mockup

How

1. After creating ideas and concepts for a game for culture, you must select some to test.
2. Once determined what to mockup, use any material/medium to create a mockup - of characters, story, levels, etc.
3. Find fast and scrappy ways to do your testing - and capture your findings to support choices and iterations.

Reflect

1. Looking back at all we have done until now, how does our mockup capture our work and thinking in the best possible way?
2. How many should we make?
3. How does our mockup highlight what is special about our game regarding culture, cultural heritage and values?

What

Pixel art tools, editors, pen/paper, etc.

Outcome

Initial mockups to decide design direction and choices.

Use

When you have game ideas to materialise and test.

Reference

Rough Mockup

Rough prototypes serve to illustrate and mediate game design ideas to team members, initiating discussions about the requirements for each touchpoint, mechanism, or interaction. This approach to prototyping aims to simulate specific game design elements and components and how they might work as a fully-fledged prototype.

45-120 minutes

Rough Mockup

How

1. The rough mockup helps explain and decide on game ideas.
2. Create a game mockup - built with paper or existing interface elements (e.g., wireframe/UI kits, game engines).
3. Use mockups(s) to visualise ideas - and consider design paths.

Reflect

1. How do we create mockups that capture our work and thinking in the best possible way?
2. What is the best mockup? Should we make more than one?
3. How can we, with our mockup, materialise different ideas that show what is unique about our game when it comes to culture, cultural heritage and values?

What

Interface elements, game engines, paper, etc.

Outcome

A tangible mockup to discuss and decide with.

Use

When a tangible and visual element is needed for decisions and iterations.

Reference

Interactive Mockup

Normally, mockups are static visual representations of a design. This approach aims to create an interactive mockup of a 'game for culture' idea - to test interactions, dependencies, and possibilities while enabling new insights about player experiences, design bugs, or revision opportunities.

45-120 minutes

Interactive Mockup

How

1. First, hand-sketch versions of all the screens your users will experience using the interface.
2. Take photos of all those screens, define buttons, and link them to matching other screens using a game engine or prototyping app.
3. With the interactive mockup, you can test the game design ideas and revisit concept art/storytelling.

Reflect

- How can we use interactive mockups to showcase players' interaction with and experience with the game ways?
- How can we, with our interactive mockup, bring the game to life in a way that highlights what is special about it regarding the player's interaction with culture, cultural heritage, and values?

What

Pen, paper, camera, game engine or prototyping app.

Outcome

A clickable, interactive mockup for testing and iteration

Use

When you need to gain insights on interactions.

Reference

Playable Prototypes

This approach aims to translate ideas and concepts into a playable prototype imbued by the different roles' responsibilities and the categories of **GAMES, CULTURE, VALUES, and CITIZENSHIP.**

A playable prototype can be digital, analogue, or hybrid - on paper, cardboard, browsers, or elsewhere. The purpose is here to transition from mockups to interactive games: by physical or digital materials.

2-6 hours

Playable Prototypes

How

1. The playable prototype might be analogue, digital, or hybrid, translating into different design constraints and considerations.
2. Draw from earlier mockups to make it playable using paper, cardboard, or digital engines. This way, you'll have more time to test and make improvements.

Reflect

1. How can we create a prototype that enables players to interact with and experience the game's core ideas, themes, and purpose?
2. What are the most important elements to make playable?
3. How does the player experience cultural worlds and empowerment in gameplay?

What

Paper or cardboard; game engine, prototyping app

Outcome

A simple but playable prototype imbued by the categories.

Use

When ready to materialise your final game idea.

Reference

Cardboard / Paper Prototypes

Paper prototyping is a widely used low-fidelity method for prototyping and testing software and interfaces through interactive paper mock-ups. In this method, different interface screens are explored and hand-sketched on paper. Despite its basic appearance, a paper prototype can be high-fidelity in navigational structure and features, providing valuable insights into these areas early throughout the design process.

2-6 hours

Cardboard / Paper Prototypes

How

1. Here, the prototypes are built quickly, using mostly paper and cardboard.
2. Concretise the initial game concept and explore its details, strengths, and weaknesses.
3. Begin with building small-scale models before creating full prototypes.

Reflect

1. How can we create paper prototypes that players can interact with?
2. How can we, through paper prototypes, convey the game's idea and the player's experience?
3. How does the paper prototype materialise culture, cultural heritage, and values in the form of a game?

What

Pen, marker, cardboard, glue, knives, scissors, camera, etc.

Outcome

A low fidelity game for culture prototype.

Use

When ready to materialise your final game idea.

Reference

Pitching Games for Culture

Crafting a pitch is relevant to communicating an idea's essence, uniqueness, and significance, targeting diverse audiences and stakeholders from different industries and sectors. On a tight time schedule, articulate the core of your game design and prototype, depending on your chosen role, while avoiding unnecessary details and emphasising the game's core elements for culture.

45-60 minutes

Pitching Games for Culture

How

1. With your game idea and prototype created - or soon to be - it's time to create a pitch.
2. Use the team's Game Log 1-4 to create a compelling pitch
3. In 1-3 minutes, you want to tell the essence of the game: its artistic, narrative, technical, and design choices. Its use and change of culture, values, and citizenship.

Reflect

1. How do you make others fall in love with your game? What is the powerful cultural story or argument for your game?
2. How have you worked with cultural heritage and values to create a powerful or innovative game?
3. How does your game make a difference? Why is it important or empowering?

What

Presentation tool or format

Outcome

Brief presentations of game for culture idea and prototype.

Use

When ready to communicate a game prototype; combine with plaque

Reference

Games for Culture Promo

This approach focuses on creating a visual and dynamic promotional video of the cultural game concept and prototype, showcasing its narrative, aesthetics, interaction design, and material function and manifestation (physical or digital).

The goal is to disseminate - show and tell - the overarching idea, novelty, and experience of a game for culture.

45-75 minutes

Games for Culture Promo

How

1. Split the game idea and prototype into elements that must be shown and explained: game elements, categories, dimensions, process, gameplay, etc.
2. Write a simple script and create a simple storyboard.
3. Film a promotional video of the game idea and prototype considering the above.

Reflect

1. How do you show the influential cultural experience players get from the game?
2. How do you showcase your game's empowering interactive gameplay and cultural game world?
3. How does your game contain and express cultural heritage and values in powerful or innovative ways to players?

What

Cameras, film editing apps, pens, papers.

Outcome

Promotional video to support communication.

Use

When ready to communicate a game prototype; combine with plaque and pitch.

Reference

Games for Culture Decision Board

This method is suited for prioritising features into "Must have," "Should have," "Could have," and "Would like but won't get" categories at a time when there is a tangible need to finalise the game prototype and concept. This approach aims to establish a clear hierarchy for implementation, resulting in a realistic and feasible work plan for the game design team..

45-60 minutes

Games for Culture Decision Board

How

1. List all features to develop within a specific time frame.
2. Make a diagram that has the four different categories: "Must have", "Should have", "Could have", or "Would like but won't get".
3. Classify the features within the four categories - and decide on the next steps and tasks.

Reflect

1. What are 'must have' features to be able to submit a game in the end?
2. What is 'must have' features to ensure your game is a game for culture created through working with values and cultural heritage
3. How much time do you have? The more time, the more features can be on the 'must have.' Features can be moved from 'should have' to 'must have' if you have time.

What

Pens, papers, post-its, markers, etc.

Outcome

Prioritised diagram of features needed in the game prototype.

Use

Before final prototyping, but after fleshing out a game design idea.

Reference

Citizens in Culture

This method aims to transform how the participants perceive objects and concepts by personifying them. Participants craft a character with a personality and a life by delving into this imaginative exercise, encouraging storytelling and outlandish traits. This method seeks to spark innovation, as the created character's traits may inspire improvements in the games for culture – and qualify the communication and dissemination of it.

45-60 minutes

Human Nature / Citizens in Culture

How

1. Choose a game scene where someone or something is required to take action.
2. Invent four scenes - and write them on paper. 1 scene = 1 paper.
3. Draw a picture of the scene with a head, arms, body, and legs - and imagine it as a living being.
4. Call out adjectives and phrases that describe it and write them down.
5. Discuss the questions below and write them down, too, and summarise the findings.

Reflect

1. What are my values?
2. What is my culture?
3. What is my citizenship?
4. What makes me different?
5. What is my mission?

What

Pen, paper, markers, etc.

Outcome

Personification of game scenes to evolve features.

Use

After fleshing out the game story, aesthetics, and interactions.

Reference

Citizen Wall

This method retrospectively examines collaborative processes by gathering individual perspectives through storytelling. Starting with a timeline on a poster, the group marks key process phases or events and discusses their significance. This method contrasts diverse viewpoints and promotes mutual understanding. Typically done post-process, i.e., late in the 'Create' phase, the method culminates in a poster capturing the group's collective perspective on the most crucial elements of the shared story.

30-45 minutes

Citizen Wall

How

1. Create a simple timeline of the joint process in the cultural game jam.
2. Individually identify key events or influences supporting or hindering game development.
3. Jointly create a citizen wall picture of your process, representing the collective understanding of it.
4. Share different perceptions and experiences - and discuss and document the process.

Reflect

1. What are the important events and influences of your teamwork and game development?
2. What were your 'pains' and 'gains'?
3. At what stages and how did culture, values, and games influence you?
4. How do your perspectives and experiences differ?

What

Flip-over, paper, pens, markers, post-its, etc.

Outcome

A process evaluation combining different perspectives.

Use

At the end of the 'Create' to support documentation and EXPO

Reference

Plaque Expo

A plaque exposition – like a poster session format – accelerates presentation planning by having participants summarise their ideas and concepts with images, fostering efficient communication without lengthy explanations. Participants create self-explanatory visual posters within 20 minutes, focusing on the "Before and After," "System," and "Process" aspects of their ideas and how they become games for culture absorbing, rekindling, transforming, or addressing culture, citizenship, and values in games.

20-30 minutes

Plaque Expo

How

1. The Plaque EXPO is vital in submitting and showcasing your game prototype - telling and showing how the game idea, concept, and prototype came together and how your game is a *game for culture*.
2. Your game's plaque is your game's submission page (frontpage)
3. Go to your team's submission front page and ensure the content is clear and aesthetically satisfactory and all elements are there.
4. Let the game jam facilitators know when the plaque is ready to be printed for the EXPO (the plaque can also be shown on a screen using a laptop)
5. The plaque should be featured next to your game for culture.

What

Paper, cardboard, pens, markers, etc.

Outcome

A 'Plaque' to display the key elements of the game idea and prototype.

Use

At the end of the 'Create' to support documentation and EXPO

Reference

END

Appendix 10.8: European Value Cards for CGJs

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European Value Cards

European Values

- **Human Dignity:** This value emphasises every individual's inherent worth and equal rights, promoting respect for human life and integrity.
- **Freedom:** In the European context, freedom involves the protection of individual liberties, ensuring people can express themselves, make choices, and participate in society without unwarranted restrictions.
- **Democracy:** European values prioritise democratic governance, where citizens have the right to participate in decision-making processes, elect representatives, and enjoy political pluralism.
- **Equality:** This value emphasises equal treatment and opportunities for all individuals, regardless of background, ensuring fairness and non-discrimination.
- **Rule of Law:** The rule of law ensures that laws apply equally to everyone, including those in power. It emphasises a legal framework that is transparent and accountable and protects individual rights.
- **Respect for Human Rights:** European values stress the importance of safeguarding fundamental rights and freedoms, as outlined in international conventions, to ensure the well-being and dignity of every person.

Human Dignity

Human dignity lies at the core of European values, reflecting a profound commitment to recognizing and upholding the intrinsic worth of every individual. It emphasises that everyone deserves respect and protection, irrespective of their background, ensuring that their inherent rights and integrity are safeguarded.

Reflections:

- How can societies and cultures ensure and consider the protection of individual dignity in various cultural contexts?
- In what ways can cultural heritage and games for culture contribute to fostering a greater understanding and appreciation of human dignity?
- What measures can be taken - through cultural heritage and games for culture - to address instances where human dignity is compromised, and how can these be addressed in and through games, culture - and at both local, national and international levels?

Freedom

Within the European framework, freedom means more than the absence of oppression; it captures the protection and promotion of individual liberties. This entails the right to express opinions, make choices, and actively participate in societal affairs without unwarranted constraints, fostering an environment where personal autonomy is valued and preserved.

Reflections:

- How can a balance between individual freedom and the need for societal order and security be struck - and how might art, culture, and games address it?
- In what areas of life, culture, and games is freedom most crucial, and are there situations where restrictions may be justifiable?
- How can advancements in society and technology be managed to safeguard personal freedom and privacy in the digital age?

Democracy

Democracy is a cornerstone of European values, embodying the principle that political power should ultimately reside in the hands of the people. This involves the right to vote in free and fair elections and the broader concept of civic engagement, encouraging citizens to participate actively in decision-making processes and ensuring a diverse political landscape.

Reflections:

- What role do art, heritage, and games play in nurturing a culture that values and enables democratic processes?
- How can art, culture, heritage, and games ensure inclusivity and representation, democracy and civic engagement?
- In what ways can citizens actively contribute to the improvement and sustainability of democratic governance?

Equality

The European value of equality underscores the commitment to a society where all individuals enjoy equal treatment and opportunities regardless of their differences. It rejects discrimination and strives for fairness, fostering an inclusive environment that enables everyone to contribute and thrive on an equal footing.

Reflections:

- How might art, games, and cultural heritage help bridge existing inequalities within diverse communities?
- How can culture and games address systemic discrimination and promote a more inclusive and equal environment?
- How can games and culture aid in fostering fair, equal, and thriving communities and societies?

Rule of Law

At the heart of European values is the concept of the *rule of law*, emphasising that legal principles and institutions should govern society. This ensures that laws are transparent, applied consistently, and hold everyone, including those in power, accountable. The rule of law protects individual rights and enables a just and orderly society.

Reflections:

- How can the rule of law be examined and problematised in games, culture, and art to ensure consistent and fair application across different segments of society?
- What challenges arise when balancing the need for security with the principles of the rule of law - and how might game for and through culture address it?
- How can citizens actively contribute to upholding the rule of law in their communities - and how can it translate into new gaming or culture experiences?

Respect for Human Rights

European values prioritise respect for human rights, acknowledging the importance of upholding fundamental freedoms and protections. Rooted in international conventions, this value protects individuals from abuse, promoting a society where everyone can live with dignity and enjoy the full range of their inherent rights without fear of discrimination or oppression.

Reflections:

- What steps can be taken to raise awareness about human rights through games and culture - and ensure local, national, and global protection?
- How can art and game-making balance cultural differences while maintaining a universal respect for human rights?
- How can games, art, and cultural heritage contribute to promoting and protecting human rights in day-to-day lives?

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Group Game Log

1-4

Overview & Instructions

Game Log 1: Experience

Materials

1. Role Cards + Method: "Empowered Participation" (Roles & Responsibilities)
2. Value Cards
3. Experience Methods
4. Transition Tool: Ideation Wheel & Ideation Capture Cards

Itch.io submission: Team's Game Page (Edit game)

Set up the frontpage for the Team's Cultural Game Jam Submission

Language: The Game Page should be written in English, so your game can be submitted and published.

At the end of the Experience Phase, the following elements should be added:

- **Game Title**
 - What is the title of your 'game for culture', and how does the title highlight your game's culture and value dimensions?
- **Team name**
 - What is your EPIC-WE team name that reflects you as a group and your 'vision' or 'mission' in the world?
- **Team members and their roles**
 - What are the names of the team members? Who are you?
 - What are your roles? What is each team member's individual responsibility/contribution in the game, in each phase of the game jam, and at the final Expo? (update this field for each phase if necessary)
 - Use the 'Role Cards' and 'Empowered Participation' Methods.

Itch.io submission: Teams Dev Log (Edit post)

At the end of the Experience Phase and before transitioning to the Play Phase, each team should create their Game Log 1 on the EPIC-WE Itch.io Submission page.

Title: Game Log 1 should have the following title: Game Log 1: Experience

Length: Elements 1-4 below can be everything from a couple of sentences to a couple of pages – it is entirely up to you

Language: The Game Log should be written in English, so your game can be submitted and published.

Instructions

The Game Log 1 should have the following structure and contain the following elements (that will be built upon in the next phase and used in the team's presentation for the Expert Council)

1. Ideation Wheel & Capture Cards

- a. Visual documentation of Ideation Wheel & Capture Cards
- b. Culture: Games with cultural heritage – Description and visual documentation of chosen culture room and cultural heritage.
- c. Value: Games with values – Description of the chosen European values.
- d. Game: Game format – Description of the chosen game format.

2. Experience Methods (For each chosen Experience Method)

- a. Name of the Method
- b. If relevant: Visual documentation of the Method and its results
- c. Outcomes/decisions: Short reflection on what came out of the Method, any decision you made based on the Method and how the outcomes of the Method will be used as you move forward in your game-making process

3. First Idea: Games through Culture

- a. Why did your team choose the culture room and cultural heritage? How might you use the cultural heritage selected as material for the game regarding aesthetics, story, design and interaction?
- b. Why did your team choose the game format? How might you use the game format selected to create a game using values and cultural heritage as game-making material?
- c. A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter' on the group's chosen cultural heritage and how it will be used as 'game-making material' to create a game through culture

4. First Idea: Games for Culture

- a. How will your team create a game for culture? How can the player experience your game as a cultural world? Why is the game important/new (to you) regarding culture/cultural heritage? What difference might the game make regarding young people and their relationships to culture and cultural heritage?
- b. How will your team create a game with value(s)? How can the player experience the value(s) in your game? Why is the game important/new (to you) when it comes to games with value(s)? What difference might the game make regarding young people and their relationship to European values and 'The European way of life'?
- c. What will your game seek to change or make possible for the player? How does your game offer new gameplay interactions or experiences to the player? How might that help create empowered participation in culture/cultural heritage (How will your game be empowering and why)?
- d. A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter' on their work as culture-makers and how they will work to create a game for culture

Game Log 2: Play

Materials

1. Role Cards + Method: "Empowered Participation" (Roles & Responsibilities)
2. Play Methods
3. Transition Tool: Expert Council & Feedback Capture Grid

Itch.io submission: Team's Game Page (Edit game)

Add the (interim) description of your Team's Cultural Game Jam Submission

At the end of the Play Phase, the following elements should be added:

Game Description

- The description is a crucial element of your game page. Take time to provide comprehensive details and enrich the description to effectively communicate your game's concept and features. Follow these points, writing at least one paragraph for each one, and be creative:
 - Which cultural values are integrated into the game?
 - How does the game intend to communicate cultural values?
 - What kind of experience and emotions are you trying to achieve for players?
 - Share insights into how the game-making process has contributed to your sense of empowerment (if possible).

Update (if necessary) ahead of presentation to Expert Council:

- **Game Title**
 - What is the title of your 'game for culture', and how does the title highlight your game's culture and value dimensions?
- **Team name**
 - What is your EPIC-WE team name that reflects you as a group and your 'vision' or 'mission' in the world?
- **Team members and their roles**
 - What are the names of the team members? Who are you?
 - What are your roles? What is each team member's individual responsibility/contribution in the game, in each phase of the game jam, and at the final Expo? (update this field for each phase if necessary)
 - Use the 'Role Cards' and 'Empowered Participation' Methods

Itch.io submission: Teams Dev Log (Edit post)

At the end of the Play Phase and before transitioning to the Imagine Phase, each team should create their **Game Log 2** on the EPIC-WE Itch.io Submission page.

Title: Game Log 2 should have the following title: Game Log 2: Play

Length: Elements 1-4 below can be everything from a couple of sentences to a couple of pages – it is entirely up to you

Language: The Game Log should be written in English, so your game can be submitted and published.

Instructions

The Game Log 2 should have the following structure and contain the following elements (that will be built upon in the next phase and used in the team's presentation for the Expert Council) Use your entry in Game Log 1: Experience as a point of departure and build upon it.

1. Play Methods (For each chosen Play Method)

- a. Name of the Method
- b. If relevant: Visual documentation of the Method and its results
- c. Outcomes/decisions: Short reflection on what came out of the Method, any decision you made based on the Method and how the outcomes of the Method will be used as you move forward in your game-making process

2. Game Concept: Games through Culture

- a. Based on your presentation to the Expert Council: How are you within your different roles using values, culture/cultural heritage as game-making material in ways that are meaningful, surprising, strange or new when it comes to your game's aesthetics, story, design and interaction? A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter'
- b. Based on the feedback from the Expert Council: Moving forward, how can the game concept work with values and culture/cultural heritage as a game-making material in even more robust and innovative ways? What will be important to focus on in the next phase when creating a game through culture? A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter'

3. Game Concept: Games for Culture

- a. Based on your presentation to the Expert Council: Focusing on value and culture/cultural heritage, what is your overall game concept? What are you trying to achieve with your game that is new? Why is it an important and different game regarding culture, empowered participation and young people? What sets your game's gameplay and player experience apart from other games? A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter' on their work as culture-makers and how they will work to create a game for culture
- b. Based on the feedback from the Expert Council: Moving forward, how can your game concept become even more important, valuable and innovative? What will be important to focus on in the next phase when creating a game for culture? A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter'

4. Expert Council Presentation & Feedback Capture Grid

- a. Visual/Written documentation of Expert Council Presentation & Feedback Capture Grid

Game Log 3: Imagine

Materials

1. Role Cards + Method: "Empowered Participation" (Roles & Responsibilities)
2. Imagine Methods
3. Transition Tool: Playtest & Gameplay Experience Capture Grid

Itch.io submission: Team's Game Page (Edit game)

Use Game Log 1 and Game Log 2 to Update/Revise the description of your Team's Cultural Game Jam Submission – see "Itch.io Submission Checklist – Teams" or itch.io submission dummy page for instructions.

You can use the Team's Game Page to briefly present your game to your playtesters before the playtest.

Itch.io submission: Teams Dev Log (Edit post)

At the end of the Imagine Phase and before transitioning to the Create Phase, each team should create their Game Log 3 on the EPIC-WE Itch.io Submission page.

Title: Game Log 3 should have the following title: Game Log 3: Imagine

Length: Elements 1-4 below can be everything from a couple of sentences to a couple of pages – it is entirely up to you

Language: The Game Log should be written in English, so your game can be submitted and published.

Instructions

The Game Log 3 should have the following structure and contain the following elements (that will be built upon in the next phase and used in the team's presentation at the Expo)

Use your entry in Game Log 2: Play as a point of departure and build upon it.

1. Imagine Methods (For each chosen Imagine Method)

- a. Name of the Method
- b. If relevant: Visual documentation of the Method and its results
- c. Outcomes/decisions: Short reflection on what came out of the Method, any decision you made based on the Method and how the outcomes of the Method will be used as you move forward in your game-making process

2. Game Mockup: Games through Culture

- a. Based on your Mockup and Playtest: How have you, in your different roles, worked with values and culture/cultural heritage as game-making material to create your Mockup regarding its aesthetics, story, design, and interaction? How did Playtesters respond to your use of value, culture/cultural heritage as game-making material? A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter'
- b. Based on the feedback from the Playtest: How can the Mockup be developed into a Prototype/Game by working with values and culture/cultural heritage as a game-making material in even more robust and more innovative ways? What will be important elements to focus on in the next phase when developing a prototype for a game through culture? A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter'

3. Game Mockup: Games for Culture

- a. Based on your Mockup and Playtest: Focusing on value and culture/cultural heritage, how is your Mockup a different or innovative game for culture? What are you trying to achieve with your game that we have not seen before, and what did the playtest tell you? What is the gameplay experience? What sets your gameplay and player experience apart from other gameplay experiences regarding culture, empowered participation and young people, and what did the playtest tell you? A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter' on their work to create an empowering gameplay experience in a game for culture
- b. Based on the feedback from the Playtest, how can the Mockup be developed into a more important, empowering, innovative Prototype/Game? What will be important to focus on in the next phase when creating an empowering gameplay experience and a game for culture? A short reflection from 'The Artist', 'The Storyteller', 'The Designer' and 'The Crafter'

4. Playtest & Gameplay Experience Capture Grid

- a. Video/Visual/Written documentation of Playtest & Gameplay Experience Capture Grid

Game Log 4: Create

Materials

1. Role Cards + Method: "Empowered Participation" (Roles & Responsibilities)
2. Create Methods
3. Transition Tool: Log & Pitch + Expo
4. Pitch (Your 'Description' on your Itch.io Team's Game Page)
5. Promo (Your 'Game video or trailer' on your Itch.io Team's Game Page)
6. Plaque Expo (Your Itch.io Team's Game Page)
7. Game for Culture (Your uploaded prototype on your Itch.io Team's Game Page)

Itch.io submission: Team's Game Page (Edit game)

- Complete the description of your game on your Team's Game Page
- Make sure to follow the "Itch.io Submission Checklist – Teams" and the itch.io submission dummy page for instructions
- Use Game Logs 1-3 to Update/Revise the description of your Team's Cultural Game Jam Submission
- When your Team's Game Page and Game Log 1-4 are finished, and your Game for Culture is ready for submission, notify the facilitators so they can do a final check of your submission before you showcase it at the EXPO and the EPIC-WE team will collect it for publication on the EPIC-WE Resource Website

Instructions (1/2)

You can use the Team's Game Page to pitch and showcase your game at the Expo

- **Game Title** (less than seven words): What is the title of your 'game for culture', and how does the title highlight your game's culture and value dimensions?
- **Team Name:** What is the name of your 'team', and how does your team name highlight who you are or what you stand for?
- **Short description**
 - Describe your game in 1-2 sentences. Try to highlight how it is a 'game through culture' and a 'game for culture' and the value, importance or innovation of the gameplay experience (Why should the player play your game? Why is it an important game?)
- **Cover image**
 - Chose a cover image for your submission that captures the essence of your game as a Game for Culture (recommended size 630x500 pixels)
- **Screenshots or photos of your game**
 - Chose images that best represent 1) your prototype as a Game for Culture (screenshots, player's experience, artwork, etc. and 2) your process of making a Game through Culture (process pictures from your work and the phases (Game Log 1-4)
- **Game video or trailer (Promo). Upload your created 'Games for Culture Promo.'**
- **Release status** (set to prototype)
- **Pricing** (set to No payments)
- **Description** (at least one paragraph for each bullet point)
 - A Game for Culture (Describe your game as a Game for Culture)
 - Your game as a Cultural world: The gameplay experience - How is your game a different or innovative game for culture? How does it express culture and values? What are you trying to change or achieve with your game for culture?
 - Your game as an example of Empowered participation in culture: The gameplayer's experience – What is the gameplay experience? Why is it important? How is it empowering to young people/gameplayers? What sets your gameplay and player experience apart from other gameplay experiences regarding aesthetics, story, design and interaction?
 - Look through Game Log 1-4 for solid arguments, sentences or reflections to pitch your game as a 'Game for Culture' in the most powerful way – What makes your game an important or powerful game for its players, and how does it create an empowering and innovative cultural experience

Instructions (2/2)

- **A Game through Culture (Describe your game as a Game through Culture)**
 - Which cultural heritage and European values have you worked with as game-making material? How did you work with it in your different aesthetics, story, design and interaction roles? How might your game-making also be considered as a form of culture-making?
 - Look through Game Logs 1-4 for solid arguments, sentences or reflections to pitch your game as a 'Game through Culture' in the most powerful way – What makes your game work with cultural heritage and values in innovative, important or meaningful ways?
- **Team members**
 - What are the names of the team members? Who are you?
 - What are your roles? What is the contribution of each team member to the game?
 - Empowered participation: Has the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam empowered you in any way – did it make a difference to you? Individually or as a team? About game-making or culture-making – and concerning thinking about or participating in culture, cultural heritage or European values? What is the most significant or valuable thing you took away from the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam?
- **Upload your files** - upload your Game for Culture (prototype) as described in the "Itch.io Submission Checklist – Teams."

Itch.io submission: Teams Dev Log (Edit post)

At the end of the Create Phase, before submitting the game and attending the EXPO, each team should create their Game Log 4 on the EPIC-WE Itch.io Submission page.

Title: Game Log 4 should have the following title: Game Log 4: Create

Length: Elements 1-4 below can be everything from a couple of sentences to a couple of pages – it is entirely up to you

Language: The Game Log should be written in English, so your game can be submitted and published.

The Game Log 4 should have the following structure and contain the following elements (that will conclude the team's game jam process)

Use your entry in Game Log 3: Imagine as a point of departure and build upon it.

Create Methods (For each chosen Create Method)

1. **Name of the Method**
2. **Visual documentation** of the Method and its results (if relevant)
3. **Outcomes/decisions:** Short reflection on what came out of the Method, any decision you made based on the Method and how the outcomes of the Method will be used as you move forward towards the Expo and Submission of your game
4. **Process Documentation** (for the Create Phase)
5. **Upload** and shortly describe any additional process documentation that you might have (e.g. video, pictures or other)

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 /epicweproject/